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**On the Effectiveness of Digital Proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners'
Listening Skills**

*A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of M.A. in
Teaching English as a Foreign Language*

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the Effect of Digital Proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners' Listening Skills. For this purpose, 100 students learning English at a language institute participated in this study. Having been homogenized by an Oxford placement test (OPT), 60 learners were selected and they were randomly assigned into two groups of 30, each control and experimental. Then both groups sat for a pre-test, which was a listening test. The purpose of this test was to measure the learners' primary proficiency in listening skill. Afterwards, the experimental group received treatment based on digital proficiency. However, the control group received no treatment and approached the traditional way of teaching. The treatment procedure took 8 sessions. Finally, at the end of the course both groups sat for the post-test listening. Then gathered data were analyzed by an Independent Sample T-test and ANCOVAs with support provided by descriptive statistics. It was explored from the study that learners' listening improves more when they are provided with digital proficiency. However, this study provides a significant contribution in curriculum innovation and policy with respect to the learners' listening development.

Key words: Digital Proficiency, Listening Skill

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.0 Introduction

Speaking and listening are categorized as oral communicative skills which are considered of great importance in the contexts of English as a foreign language (EFL). Since the main purpose of learning a foreign language is communication, searching for new techniques which help learners enhance their oral skills, listening and speaking is important (Ganji Khoosf & Khosravani, 2014). Several techniques and tools have been introduced and employed in EFL settings in order to enhance students' speaking and listening skills. With the advent of technology EFL contexts have experienced significant changes. Technology has changed every aspect of human life in general and foreign language learning (FLL) process, in specific. According to Haider and Chowdhury (2012), the emergence of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) has resulted in significant changes in the arena of language teaching and learning starting from the use of innovative learning materials to the widening of interaction patterns among a huge and diverse community of learners. There have been arguments with respect to the advantages and disadvantages of CALL, though the trend of employing computer assisted tools in language teaching is increasing throughout the world (ibid). CALL has played a key role in personalizing education (Ghalami Nobar & Ahangari, 2012). Only when learners are able to take benefit from each learning opportunity rather than simply responding to

different stimuli from the teacher can they be skillful manipulation of language in their language learning process (Ying, n.d.). The situation demands the urgent need of enhancing learners' initiatives and learner autonomy (ibid). Schmenk, (2005) states that: 'The popularity of

learner autonomy may be at least partially related to the rise of computer technology and the growing importance of computers in language learning environments worldwide' (P.107).

Hence due to the popularity of computer use in EFL contexts the present study aims at exploring the effect of Digital proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Listening besides the three other alleged major skills involved in second language learning process has always been an issue of great importance. Listening causes effective communication, which is an essential factor contributing to daily life that nowadays teachers should take into account. This Cinderella Skill (Nunan, 1999) with its rich pedagogical literature has much influence on learning other parallel skills, as listeners are continually decoding original meaning of the speaker using incoming sounds as clues. Putting a wrong interpretation on listening as a passive task is a highly common thought which is of course not right, because it is an active operation that requires mental processing.

Not only listening skills contribute greatly to the development of all other language skills, but also it improves the oral interaction of the learners and boost their confidence as well. Complex process of Listening is often used as an instrument to help learners understand the spoken language (Rost, 1990). Lack of this important skill will make barriers to encode the input or message which is the most important part of communication, therefore the process of making output is disturbed. Becoming an ideal listener is one of the goals that L2 learners usually face many problems reaching. Vandergrift (2007) claimed that,

Research into L2 listening is important because a better understanding of the process will inform pedagogy. Students who learn to control their listening processes can enhance their comprehension. This, in turn, affects the development of other skills and overall success in L2 learning. As Dr. Kline (1996) asserted, to learn 'how to listen' is an effortful task, however the result is worthy.

Considering Krashen's input hypothesis, in order to help language learners to speak, it is essential to provide them with enough input. The speaker, listener, and physical setting are factors that also make an impact on learners' listening skills.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

As it was mentioned earlier, the present study aims to compare EFL learners' who are equipped with the knowledge of digital skills and the influence on their listening skills.

Does having digital proficiency affect Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills?

Does Lack of digital proficiency affect Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills?

Two different features of investigation are tracked by the current study: first, Theoretical aspect which presents new curriculum design teaching the listening ability parallel to digital proficiency skills. Secondly, the practical aspect hoping to be useful for teachers, curriculum developers and learners who are teaching or learning listening skills.

1.3 Research Question

The main question raised by this study is to compare the EFL learners' who have a good knowledge of digital skills with those who lack these skills when investigating the achievement in listening skills.

RQ1: Does digital proficiency **affect** Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills?

1.4 Research hypothesis

To answer the research questions raised the following null hypothesis have been contrived:

H01: Digital proficiency does not affect Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills.

1.5 Significance of the study

In the grand scheme of things, listening comprehension has had a relatively short but trying history that has been subject to internal and external influences such as teacher and student opinions and motivation, the design and presentation of aural material, and the technologies available, all of which can affect a student's ability to process listening comprehension texts. Thankfully, today's knowledge of instructional design and technology allows us to present information in various modes (visual, aural, or text) to help increase students' acquisition or construction of new knowledge. However, such results have not come without a great deal of trial and error, success and failure, and both technological and pedagogical evolution.

1.6 Definition of key terms

The important terms used throughout this study are as follows:

Digital Proficiency: is an umbrella term that includes any communication device or application, encompassing radio, television, cellular phones, computer and network hardware and software, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them, such as videoconferencing and distance learning.

Digital proficiency is a measure of how effectively individuals and organizations engage with digital technology for both internal and external stakeholder benefit. Today, technology impacts every facet of our lives, from how we communicate and collaborate, how we learn and how we gather, synthesize and disseminate information. It accounts for how individuals and organizations innovate, solve problems, improve productivity, make decisions and even leapfrog competitors. Fischer (1994)

- Desktop and web applications
- Mobile and smart devices
- Collaboration tools
- Social networks

Listening Skills: Is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This involves understanding a speakers' accent or pronunciation, his or her grammar and vocabulary, and grasping the meaning conveyed. (Saricoban,1999).

1.7 Summary

Chapter one begins with an introduction, introducing the background of the variables under investigation. It follows with the statement of the problem and the purpose of the study, research question, hypothesis and significance of the study and finally it ends up by the operational definitions of key terms.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

Listening plays an important role in communication as it is said that, of the total time spent communicating, listening takes up 40-50%; speaking, 25-30%; reading, 11-16%; and writing, about 9% (Mendelsohn, 1994). Although the teaching of listening comprehension has long been somewhat neglected and poorly taught aspect of English in many EFL programs (Mendelsohn, 1994, p. 9), listening is now regarded as much more important in both EFL classrooms and SLA research. Listening involves an active process of deciphering and constructing meaning from both verbal and non-verbal messages (Nunan, 1998). Thus, the label of passive skill applied to listening is a misnomer. This misunderstanding may stem from the fact that superficial learners seem to only sit in a language lab quietly, listen to pre-recorded dialogues, and write the answers to some questions related to the oral stimulus. It is evident, then, that listening is not as passive 'as it has been claimed to be as it demands a number of complicated processes on the part of the learners. There are two subsuming cognitive processes: bottom-up (data-driven) and top-down (conceptually driven). The bottom-up processing involves constructing meaning from the smallest unit of the spoken language to the largest one in a linear mode (Nunan, 1998). Thus, the learners attempt to understand a spoken discourse by decoding a number of sounds to form words. Next, a nexus of words is linked to form phrases, which make up sentences. These sentences build a complete text, the meaning of which is then constructed by the listeners. In addition to the grammatical relationships, such suprasegmental phonemes as stress, rhythm and intonation also substantially contribute to this data-driven processing (van Duzer, 1997).

Learners can be trained to perform this processing, for instance, by activities that require them to discriminate two sounds or distinguish rising and falling intonations. The top-down processing, on the other hand, refers to interpreting meaning as intended by the speakers by means of schemata or structures of knowledge in the mind (Nunan, 1998). This view emphasizes the prominence of background knowledge already possessed by the learners in making sense of the information they hear. In the aural perception, the prior knowledge may facilitate their attempt to grasp the incoming information by relating the familiar with the new one, and significant lack of such knowledge can hamper their efforts to comprehend a particular utterance. It is, therefore, essential that learners are accustomed to performing this processing, usually by extracting the gist of the exchange they listen to.

Due to the fact that the communicative approach is increasingly used in EFL situation, we, therefore, stress the importance of students' communicative competence. The need for competence in listening in EFL English language learners is increasing, so that listening teaching has attracted considerable attention. Unfortunately, the teaching of listening skills is still neglected in the English language teaching process. EFL learners have serious problems in English listening comprehension due to the fact that universities pay more attention to English grammar, reading and vocabulary. Listening and speaking skills are not important parts of many course books or curricula and teachers do not seem to pay attention to these skills while designing their lessons. EFL English language learners have limited listening comprehension. Listening levels of learners are different from each other, because listening is affected by crucial factors. The most important factors that should be emphasized are: the significance of listening, the study of listening teaching theory and use of the most advanced listening teaching methods. In many English language classes, grammar-translation method is used for teaching. This method

has been found inadequate to the demands for producing efficient English speakers and listeners. So a new teaching method should be used to meet the needs of students. This new method is called communicative approach. English must be taught as a tool for communication. It is now widely accepted that students' listening ability must be at the core of teaching practice, and it is the area in which teachers need to concentrate their own efforts to improve their teaching. This is a significant challenge for English teachers; however, it is crucial in the development of English language communicative competence. The purpose of this approach is to improve the students' English overall linguistic capability and oral and aural competence. The researchers attempt to discuss the definition of listening and importance of listening. Then, they review the process of listening comprehension, strategies of listening comprehension. Analysis of listening comprehension problems is reviewed. Then, teaching methods for listening comprehension and teaching listening activities will be discussed. Finally, general principles in teaching listening comprehension are discussed. Findings of this study will be beneficial to EFL learners to improve their English language listening comprehension ability.

2.1 Theoretical framework

Whether using digital tools such as personal computers, tablets, and smart phones for purchasing goods or involvement in socialistic activities, the use of digital aspect of our life is inevitable, therefore the usage of this aspect in Language teaching seems to be a sensible choice. Nowadays it seems that students mostly tend to use computer-based materials, however the way to use these types of material need specific skills (Gulek & Demirtas, 2005). The umbrella term of 'Digital Proficiency' includes the mentioned skills, which also refers to the concept of digital literacy which sometimes have been used also as synonyms. This concept represents the ability

of people benefiting from digital environment accomplishing tasks (Jones-Kavalier & Flannigan, 2008).

Talking about technology in the landscape of language teaching and not referring to CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) seems to be impossible. CALL as Beatty defines is the process through which the learner uses computer to improve language skills

(2003). During the history of CALL some researchers have accused the framework for being overly technology driven (Salaberry, 2001), however it is not logical to deny the effectiveness of this concept on further significant researches in this era. With constant development in the world of technology, and with the growing need for authentic conversation to promote listening skills, the classes are becoming more and more equipped with modern digital facilities. By usage of computer-based materials, through internet and many websites' teachers can provide learners with great amount of authentic audio and visual material, to help learners gain the opportunity of making comprehensible output and input (Chapelle, 1999). By means of podcasts (the delivery of on-demand audio and video files through the web), which has positive effect on the listening instructions (Phuong, 2014), and according to the related researchers a positive attitude toward the usage of computer-based materials is shown. Bearing this in mind the ability to use digital technologies shows a very significant role shaping current teaching and learning landscape, or in other words, digital proficiency comes along.

To follow up the concept of digital competence is raised, which as a gradually developing concept appears to be a multi-facet target. In our time being digitally competent means being able to understand the media and fulfilling the need to be involved and critical about the information gained (Ferarri, 2012). Finally digital expertise, which is the ideal level of reaching

digital proficiency in order to achieve listening skills is raised, that refers to being able to complete highly professional tasks, such as managing, preparing, conducting, and creating data.

2.2 What is Listening?

According to Anderson and Lynch (1988), arguing what is successful listening, understanding is not something that happens because of what a speaker says: the listener has a crucial part to play in the process, by activating various types of knowledge, and by applying what he knows to what he hears and trying to understand what the speaker means (p.6). Underwood (1989) simplified the definition of listening to "the activity of paying attention to and trying to get meaning from something we hear" (p. 1). Mendelsohn (1994) defines listening comprehension as —the ability to understand the spoken language of native speakers. O ‘Malley, Chamot, and Kupper (1989) offer a useful and more extensive definition that listening comprehension is an active and conscious process in which the listener constructs meaning by using cues from contextual information and from existing knowledge, while relying upon multiple strategic resources to fulfill the task requirement (p.19). Mendelsohn (1994) points out that, in listening to spoken language, the ability to decipher the speaker’s intention is required of a competent listener, in addition to other abilities such as processing the linguistic forms like speech speed and fillers, coping with listening in an interaction, understanding the whole message contained in the discourse, comprehending the message without understanding every word, and recognizing different genres. Listeners must also know how to process and how to judge what the illocutionary force of an utterance is- that is, what this string of sounds is intended to mean in a particular setting, under a particular set of circumstances – as an act of real communication (Mendelsohn, 1994).

Purdy (1997) defined listening as "the active and dynamic process of attending, perceiving, interpreting, remembering, and responding to the expressed (verbal and nonverbal), needs, concerns, and information offered by other human beings" (p. 8). Listening comprehension is an inferential process (Rost, 2002). Linguistic knowledge and world knowledge interact as listeners create a mental representation of what they hear. Bottom up and top-down processes are applied to get to this mental representation and achieve comprehension. Rost (2002) defined listening as a process of receiving what the speaker actually says, constructing and representing meaning, negotiating meaning with the speaker and responding, and creating meaning through involvement, imagination and empathy. To listen well, listeners must have the ability to decode the message, the ability to apply a variety of strategies and interactive processes to make meaning, and the ability to respond to what is said in a variety of ways, depending on the purpose of the communication. Listening involves listening for thoughts, feelings, and intentions. Doing so requires active involvement, effort and practice (Shen, Guizhou, Wichura, Kiattichai, 2007). To sum up, it is widely admitted that listening comprehension is not merely the process of a unidirectional receiving of audible symbols, but an interactive process (Brown, 2001). In the eight processes of comprehension (Clark & Clark, 1977; Brown, 2001) the hearer, after receiving the information, assigns a literal meaning to the utterance first and then assigns an intended meaning to the utterance. A key to human communication is the ability to match perceived meaning with intended meaning.

2.3 Definition of listening

According to Howatt & Dakin (1974), listening is the capacity to plumb and understand what others are saying. This process entails understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, the speaker's grammar and vocabulary, and comprehension of meaning. A genuine listener is

capable of performing these above-mentioned items simultaneously. Thomlinson's (1984) definition of listening shed light on active listening, which goes beyond comprehending as understanding the message content, to comprehension as an act of empathetic understanding of the speaker which hints the cognitive domain of this hydra-headed issue, listening. Furthermore, Gordon (1985) stated that empathy is vital for listening and contended that it is more than a polite attempt to identify a speaker's perspectives. Rather more importantly, empathetic understanding expands to egocentric prosodies behavior.

Thus, the listener altruistically acknowledges concern for the speaker's welfare and interests. Having defined listening as an active process requiring the same skills of prediction, hypothesizing, checking, revising, and generalizing that writing and reading demand, Ronald & Roskelly (1985) present specific exercises to make students active listeners who are aware of the inner voice one hears when writing; Language learning relies on listening since it provides the aural input that serves as the basis for language acquisition and enables learners to interact in spoken communication.

Listening is the first language mode that everyone acquires when dealing with it naturally. It provides the foundation for all aspects of language and cognitive development, and it plays a life-long role in the process of communication. Wilt (1950), in a widely-cited study (e.g., Martin, 1987;) revealed that people listen 45% of the time they spend communicating. Wilt found that 30% of communication time was spent on speaking, 16% on reading, and 9% on writing. This finding confirmed what Rankin discovered in 1928, that people spent 70% of their waking time communicating and three-fourths of this time was spent on listening and speaking.

According to Bulletin (1952; cited in Wills, 2008), listening is the fundamental language skill. It is the medium through which people gain a large portion of the issue related to their

education, their information, their understanding of the world and of human affairs, their ideals, sense of values, and their appreciation. In this day of mass communication, much of it oral, it is of vital importance that students are taught to listen effectively and critically. Based on Krashen (1987), language input is the most essential condition of language acquisition. As an input skill, listening plays a crucial role in students' language development. Krashen (1987) argues that people acquire language by understanding the linguistic information they hear. Acquisition is achieved mainly through receiving input and listening ability is the critical component in achieving language input.

2.4 The nature of listening

Listening involves identifying information, relating that information to those memories, filling it in the proper spot (or) creating a new place for it, and using it when needed. Hirsch (1986) stated listening as an aspect of skills; involves neurological response and interpretations of sounds to understand and to give meaning by reacting, selecting meaning, remembering, attending, analyzing and including previous experience (p.23). Lundsteen (1979, as cited in Richards, 2001) also pointed out that listening is highly complex, interactive process that has been defined as the process by which spoken language is converted to meaning in the mind. So far as this definition connotes, listening is more than just hearing (p. 25). As is obviously implied, the difference between the two presumably falls in the continuum that listening is much more consciously, if not intentionally in the control of listener. Rivers (1981) from another viewpoint stated: Listening is a critical element in learning any foreign language. It helps the learner to acquire competence in language, and he can exhibit his competence if he is communicating at school, at work or in the community. In normal course of the day listening is

used nearly twice as much as speaking and four to five times as much as reading and writing (p.27).

By the same token, Nunan (1999) claimed that "we listen as much as twice as we speak (p. 27). Wolvin and Coakley (1988) stated, listening was regarded crucial for communication at work at any level for employment, job success, and general career competence and for effective relationship between supervisor and subordinates (p. 145). Morley (1991) states despite the recognition of the critical role that listening skills play in communication and acquisition of language; it remains one of the least understood skills in language learning (p.145).

Pearson (1983) stated, "Listening involves the simultaneous organization and combination of skills in Phonology, Syntax, Semantics, and knowledge of the text structure, all of which seem too be controlled by the cognitive process. Therefore, it can be said that, though not fully realized, listening skills are essential in acquiring language proficiency" (p.125). The importance of listening cannot be ignored as it is the first step towards language learning.

2.5 The difficulty of listening

As Brown (2001) and Flowerdew (2005) outlined, the difficulty of listening goes back to its nature. Here are some of those features in brief. Clustering: In written language we are conditioned to attend to the sentence as the basic unit of organization. In spoken language, due to the memory limitations and our predisposition for 'chunking' or 'clustering', we break down speech into smaller groups of words. In teaching listening comprehension, therefore, you need to help students to pick out manageable cluster of words. In most listening situations, the aim is not to remember the specific words, or phrases used but to extract the main ideas or information.

Redundancy: Spoken language unlike most written language has a good deal of redundancy. In conversations we notice the re-phrasings, repetitions, elaborations, and little insertions of 'I mean' and 'you know'. Such redundancy can help the hearer to process meaning by offering more time and extra information. Learners can train themselves to profit from such redundancy by first being aware that not every new sentence or phrase will necessarily contain new information by looking for the signals of redundancy.

Reduced forms: While spoken language does indeed contain a good deal of redundancy, it also has many reduced forms. Reduction can be phonological (Djeetyet? for Did you eat yet?), morphological (contractions like I'll), syntactic (elliptical forms like 'When will you be back? Tomorrow, maybe'), or pragmatic (phone rings in a house and child answers and yells to another room in the house, Mom! Phone!). These reductions pose significant difficulties, especially for classroom learners who may have initially been exposed to the full forms of the English language. **Performance variables:** In spoken language, except for planned discourse (speech, lectures, etc.). Hesitations, false starts, pauses, and corrections are common.

Native listeners are conditioned from very young ages to weed out such performance variables, whereas they easily interfere with comprehension in second language learners.

Colloquial language: Learners who have been exposed to standard written English and / or textbook language sometimes find it surprising and difficult to deal with colloquial language.

Idioms, slang, reduced forms, and shared cultural knowledge are all manifested at some point in conversations.

Rate of delivery: (Speed & Pause) Learners will eventually need to be able to comprehend language delivered at varying rates of speed and, at times, delivered with few pauses. **Stress, rhythm, and intonation:** As English is a stress-time language, English speech can

be a terror for some learners as mouthfuls of syllables come spilling out between stress points. Also, intonation patterns are very significant not just for interpreting straightforward elements such as questions, statements, and emphasis but for understanding more subtle messages like sarcasm, endearment, insult, solicitation, praise, etc.

Interaction: Conversation is subject to all the rules of interaction: negotiation, clarification, signals, turn-taking, and topic nomination, maintenance, and termination. Therefore, to learn to listen is also to learn to respond and to continue a chain.

2.6 Theoretical issues in listening

Listening has some theoretical frameworks, some of which are repetitively quoted in the literature.

2.6.1 Models (Theories) of listening

Besides a simplistic view, the way how one understands what s/he hears has got a neurological perspective. Other than that, based on the nature and mechanisms of listening, several theories of models of comprehension depiction current knowledge and technology and related disciplines have been developed. As it has been mentioned, these four strands are complementary rather than mutually exclusive (Lynch, 1996; Mendelson, 1998; cited in Schmitt, 2002).

2.6.1.1 Communication Theory model (CTM)

Communication theory or more aptly as Shannon & Weaver (1949) tagged "the mathematical theory of communication" (p. 127) comes to vogue the telecommunication systems. CTM brings back the terms of 'transmission', 'signal' 'reception' and 'noises'. The center of concern here is on intelligibility rather than perception. It should be noted that so far as

it was developed for solving engineering problems, the human participation is peripheral (Licklider & Miller, 1951; as cited in Kaplan, 2002). Communication theory researchers assumed their work did not merely reflect comprehension; however, CTM realizes thinking about the ways in which comprehension could not be characterized in terms of straightforward 'reception' of message (Lynch, 1996; Mendelson, 1998; cited in Schmitt, 2002).

2.6.1.2 Information processing model (IPM)

This model is strongly highlighted by research in computing and artificial intelligence. The concepts of input, processing and output are key concepts. In this regard, human beings are considered as a "limited processor, when doing complex tasks, one have to devote more attention to one aspect of task and less to another" (cited in Schmitt, 2002, p. 195). As Anderson (1985) aptly mentioned typical information processing models are 'Perception, Parsing and utilization'. By the same token, Brown (2000) stated that IPM includes 'identify, Search, File and Use'. The similar stages between the two theorists are 'stages of understanding'. It also recognizes that "listeners are only able to achieve real - time processing by resorting to Parallel Distribution Process" (Lynch, 1996; Mendelson, 1998; cited in Schmitt, 2002, p.195). Lynch (1996) and, Mendelson (1998) (as cited in Schmitt, 2002) came up with the idea that information processing is the simultaneous integration of information from multiple resources and 'bottom-up' and 'top-down' processing.

2.6.1.3. Social / Contextual model (SCM)

In this model, human beings are considered much more than a limited processor. Ohta (2000) stated that "comprehension is seen as cognitive process... that unites the social and the individual" (cited in Richards, 2001). In SCM, human beings, in contrast to CTM and IPM are seen as participants and in formation of meaning and creators of meaning in which listening is

interactional in the nature. Sperber & Wilson (1995) argued that even in constrained contexts, meaning is negotiated among conversational partners, maintaining that they follow meaning negotiation in a "mutual cognitive environment" (Sperber & Wilson, 1995; p. 61; cited in Fiel 2008). The concept of context here is awarded a pivotal role.

2.6.1.4. Situated Action model (SAM)

The pivotal issue in this model is that people spend much of their time trying to understand order to do things rather than to store information in memory. Barsalou (1999; cited in Schmi 2002) stated that the language emerged from the need to control others' actions (i.e. In activities like hunting gathering etc.) The supporters of SAM see the daily interaction as a future-oriented action.

2.7 Strategies of Listening Comprehension

One of the methods learners can become actively involved in controlling their own learning is by using strategies. Vandergrift (1999) showed —Strategy development is important for listening training because strategies are conscious means by which learners can guide and evaluate their own comprehension and responses. In O'Malley, Chamot, Stewner-Manzanares, Kupper, and Russo's (1985) study, high school ESL students were randomly assigned to receive learning strategy training on vocabulary, listening, and speaking tasks and the result indicated strategy training can be effective for integrative language tasks. Nakata (1999) studied the influence of listening strategy training on Japanese EFL learners' listening competence, and it showed that the effect of listening strategy training was more discernible on perception than on comprehension, especially for those students who received low scores on the G-TELP.

Research into speech perception has shown that listening comprehension involves far more than mere decoding of the sounds. Rivers (1983b) in her discussion of speech perception identifies three stages. First, the listener must recognize that the sounds are an actual message and not just noise. This recognition means to the listener that the sounds are elements of the language system. In the second stage the listener identifies sounds along with lexical and syntactic forms by segmenting and grouping them. The third stage involves recording in order to retain the auditory message in long-term storage. These stages are necessarily rapid and overlapping. Whether the process of listening comprehension is as described above or in some other form, it is certainly an active process involving cognitive processing (pp. 80-83).

Native speakers and highly proficient second language learners complete the complex process of speech comprehension smoothly. Second language learners at lower levels of language proficiency whether it be due to a lack of auditory experience with varying accents, limited vocabulary, imperfect control of the syntactic and semantic structure of the language, or other limitations with regard to the elements necessary for communicative competency © 2011 ACADEMY PUBLISHER 981 need to rely on listening strategies to assist them in comprehending the aural communication. Brown (1995) quite appropriately compares strategies to battle plans: Strategies are specific methods of approaching a problem or task, modes of operation for achieving a particular end, planned designs for controlling and manipulating certain information. They are contextualized —battle plans‖ that might vary from moment to moment, or day to day, or year to year (p. 104).

Among all the strategies for listening, O'Malley and Chamot (1990) claimed three main types of strategies: meta-cognitive, cognitive and social strategies. The meta-cognitive strategy was a kind of self-regulated learning. It included the attempt to plan, check, monitor, select,

revise, and evaluate, etc. For example, for meta-cognitive planning strategies, learners would clarify the objectives of an anticipated listening task, and attend to specific aspects of language input or situational details that assisted in understanding the task (Vandergrift, 1999). Generally, it can be discussed through pre-listening planning strategies, while-listening monitoring strategies, and post-listening evaluation strategies.

The cognitive strategies are related to comprehending and storing input in working memory or long-term memory for later retrieval. They are investigated from the aspects of bottom-up strategies, top-down strategies. For bottom-up processing, it refers to using the incoming input as the basis for understanding the message. Comprehension begins with the received data that is analyzed as successive levels of organization-sounds, words, as a process of decoding. For bottom-up strategies, Henner-Stanchina (1987) engaged in a similar study and pointed out that effective listeners were good at using their previous knowledge and experience to raise hypotheses about a text, integrating new information into their ongoing interpretations, making influences to bridge gaps, assessing their interpretations, and modifying their hypotheses, if necessary. On the other hand, top-down processing went from meaning to language (Richards, 2008). Learners can try to predict what will utter by the signal. However, Chiu (2006) claimed that listening comprehension was neither top-down nor bottom-up processing. Simultaneously, Lu (2008) summed up that the scholars believed the listeners not only utilized bottom-up but also top-down processing models. In sum, Thompson & Rubin (1996) indicated the effects of meta-cognitive and cognitive strategy instruction on the listening comprehension performance of American university students learning Russian. They found that the subjects who received strategy instruction in listening to video-recorded texts improved significantly over those who had received no instruction.

For social/ affective strategies, Vandergrift (2003) defined the strategies as the techniques listeners used to collaborate with others, to verify understanding or to lower anxiety. Habte-Gabr (2006) stated that socio-affective strategies were those which were nonacademic in nature and involve stimulating learning through establishing a level of empathy between the instructor and student. They included considering factors such as emotions and attitudes (Oxford, 1990). It was essential for listeners to know how to reduce the anxiety, feel confident in doing listening tasks, and promote personal motivation in improving listening competence (Vandergrift, 1997). According to O'Malley & Chamot (1990), among the four strategies of management strategies, social strategies, cognitive strategies, affective strategies in listening comprehension, both social and affective strategies influenced the learning situation immediately.

A great deal has been written about language strategies. These strategies have been categorized as learning strategies and communication strategies. Ellis (1985:181) has stated that, communication strategies are problem-oriented. That is they are employed by the learner because he lacks or cannot gain access to the linguistic resources required to express an intended meaning. They are —short-term answers while learning strategies Ellis points are —long-term solutions. In general, discussion of and research on these communication strategies have focused on the learner's behavior when his production in the second language shuts down. Little research has focused specifically on strategies employed when the learner finds he cannot comprehend the auditory message. This research specifically intended to address the question of what strategies the listener employed to solve the problem when he/she failed to comprehend the message he/she was listening to. The listener 's level of language competency was considered an important variable in the listener 's choice of strategy. Paterson (2001:90) states that —Strategy use varies

with proficiency and so the relationship between strategy use and proficiency level is an important one.

2.8 Theories of listening comprehension

2.8.1 Bottom-up listening

Example: listening to directions from a friend on how to get to his/her house. This kind of listening comprehension is achieved by dividing and decoding the sounds - bit by bit. The ability to separate the stream of speech into individual words becomes more important here, if we are to recognize, for example, the name of a street or instructions on how to take a particular bus. Understanding vocabulary and other specific parts of speech is also very important for this kind of listening.

2.8.2 Top-down listening

Example: listening to a friend tell a story about a terrible vacation in Thailand during rainy season with a mutual friend. This kind of listening requires the use of background knowledge in understanding the meaning of the message. Background knowledge consists of context. Do you ever get your students to predict the content of a listening beforehand, maybe using information about the topic or situation, pictures, or key words? If so, you are helping them to develop their top-down processing skills.

2.9 Contemporary theories of listening comprehension

The “old school” way of teaching was bottom-up but then shifted to more top-down listening processes. There are good reasons for this given that learners need to be able to listen effectively even when faced with unfamiliar vocabulary or structures but nowadays most

educators agree that it should be a mix of both processes. Successful listening depends on the ability to combine these two types of processing.

2.9.1 Reciprocal (two ways)

Another way of characterizing listening is in terms of whether the listener is also required to take part in the interaction. This is known as reciprocal listening. - Reciprocal listening is face-to-face- The listener has the opportunity to answer back, clarify understanding, or check that he or she has comprehended correctly.

2.9.2 Non-Reciprocal (one way)

In non-reciprocal listening the listener is not required to participate.- Non-reciprocal listening tasks can draw on a rich variety of authentic data, not just lectures and text-book dialogues.-Some examples of non-reciprocal listening materials are: answering machine messages, store announcements on public transportation, mini lectures, and narrative recounts.

2.9.3 Extensive

Listening for main ideas – just getting the gist. “Does the speaker have a positive or negative opinions about Italian food?” is an example of a question we could ask in an extensive listening activity. Listening without being constrained by pre-set questions or tasks. Listening at or below one's comfortable fluent listening ability. No difficult tasks.

2.9.4 Intensive

Involves more detailed analysis of the language used or listening for specific information. “What is the speaker’s favorite Italian food?” is an example of a question we could ask in an intensive listening activity. Intensive listening is also used for the study of a language point: finding adjectives or highlighting specific grammar forms.

2.10 Empirical Research about Listening Comprehension

The first attempt to investigate empirically the notion of listening comprehension was that of DeFilippis' (1980) with a study that analyzed and compared the listening strategies of skillful and unskillful L2 learners in French. On the basis of raw test scores on the MLA Cooperative Foreign Language Test in French, DeFilippis identified the top thirteen students as skillful listeners, and the bottom thirteen students as unskillful listeners. DeFilippis elicited the listening strategies of research participants by using a test instrument consisting of a series of audio-taped aural comprehension tasks at five developmental levels. This test was administered to each subject within the parameters of a semi-structured interview. The findings indicated that while skillful listeners answered more questions correctly and requested fewer playbacks of the aural comprehension tasks, the listening strategies of both groups were similar. Another study in the processes and strategies of listening was conducted by Martin (1982). This investigation was a case study and was developed in three stages with five ESL native Spanish speaking consultants participating in nine 50-minute interviews. Much of the data was collected in interviews which consisted of immediate retrospective think aloud reporting. The listening strategies described by the consultants were categorized into two groups: 21 on the word level and 13 on the idea level. While the former were used to associate meaning with specific words, the latter dealt with the establishment of a topic and the association of subsequent meanings to the main idea.

L2 empirical studies have also found that there is a high degree of positive transfer between a listening-only initial focus and other language skills, while lower scores were reported in all language skills when learners were required to develop simultaneously the skills of

speaking and listening (Gary, 1978). A listening-only initial focus has been found to yield a significant affective advantage for foreign/ second language learners, increasing their effectiveness and concentration in language learning.

Some of the empirical evidence that gives support to the importance of listening in second/ foreign language acquisition was provided by Feyten's (1991) study of ninety students of French and Spanish. Feyten worked with 36 students of French and 54 students of Spanish who enrolled in the summer intensive program at the University of Tennessee. The program included aspects of proficiency-oriented instruction in that the oral skills were emphasized. Participants were asked to respond to the video version of WBLT at the beginning of the program, and this was set as the pretest for this study. At the end of the program, the subjects completed the Foreign Language Test that consisted of an oral interview, a listening comprehension component, and a written grammar, reading, and vocabulary component. The qualitative data of the pretest was quantified so that the pretest and posttest data were compared. To determine the relationship between listening ability and foreign language proficiency, simple bivariate correlations were computed.

Attia (2002) conducted a study to investigate the effect of a strategy-based instruction program on developing EFL listening comprehension skills. The main purpose of this study was to probe empirically the effects of three different approaches: strategy training, metacognitive instruction and pure exposure, on listening performance, attitudes, self-efficacy, and on strategy knowledge, use and perceived value among student teachers of English in Egypt. Moreover, the interaction between these three treatments and students' proficiency levels (high/low) was an item of interest. The results of the study demonstrated that strategy training is better in promoting all the variables addressed and compares favorably with metacognitive instruction and pure

exposure. Results also showed that the strategy training approach holds great potential for developing students' independence and that it moved them towards autonomy. Furthermore, the findings indicated that the metacognitive instruction group performed significantly better than the control group only in listening and attitudes. Amin, Amin, & Aly (2011) conducted a study entitled "A Correlation Study between EFL Strategic Listening and Listening Comprehension Skills among Secondary School Students". Eighty secondary school students participated in this study. Participants' strategic listening was measured by a Strategic Listening Interview (SLI), a Strategic Listening Questionnaire (SLQ) and a Strategic Listening Checklist (SLC) with think-aloud protocol. Their listening comprehension skills were measured by an EFL listening comprehension test. A Pearson correlation analysis was run to test the correlation between strategic listening and listening comprehension test scores. The findings revealed that the relationship between strategic listening and listening comprehension was positive and significant. The higher the level of strategic listening these students obtained, the higher the score they attained on the listening comprehension test and vice versa. Carissa (1997) investigated the possible existence of a sequence of use of listening comprehension strategies by advanced ESL learners. Although the results revealed that these students had a similar pattern of strategy use regardless of their gender and English achievement, those students with higher ability in listening comprehension tended to use the following six strategies more often than the other students: self-evaluation, summarization, elaboration, inference, feedback, and reprise. Murphy (1985, as reported in Carissa 1997) worked with 12 intermediate university students and concluded that the high achievers used their prior knowledge, made guesses (inferring), and monitored their comprehension more often than did low achievers. Kasper (1984) has conducted an exploratory study on reception in aural communication focusing on FL learners'

comprehension of speech act and discourse functions, referred to as 'pragmatic comprehension', in role-play situations of learner-native speaker discourse. The situations were between German learners of English and native speakers. This study looked into the types of learners' pragmatic misunderstanding; that is their failure to understand the native speaker's communicative intention. The data analysis indicated that the learners relied too heavily on bottom-up processing. This study explored the aspect of pragmatic comprehension in aural communication; however, it did not address the question about listeners' specific comprehension problems or how they solved such problems.

2.11 How to teach Listening comprehension

Some of the teaching methods for improving students' listening comprehension skill are as follows:

2.11.1 Cultivating Students' Listening Skills

Cultivating students' listening skills is one of the most difficult tasks for any ESL teacher. This is because successful listening skills are acquired over time and with lots of practice. The demands of the task are often frustrating for students because there are no precise rules, as in grammar teaching. Speaking and writing also have very specific exercises that can lead to improvement. However, there are quite specific ways of improving listening skills, but these are difficult to quantify. Teachers must develop students' micro skills of listening comprehension. Brown (1994) identifies seventeen listening comprehension micro skills. Some of the more important of these skills are discussed here. For beginners, the most important listening skill is discrimination in English pronunciation, intonation and language flow. They need to acquire the crucial skill of identifying the main information. Wu Zhengfu (1991) recognizes that when students acquire basic discrimination ability, they can select and analyze the meaning of what

they hear and grasp the main content. In the teaching process teachers should cultivate students' ability to select main information and instruct students to control the general meaning of listening materials on the whole. In class, for example, teachers can ask students to listen to the general meaning of the passage, and to sum up key points and main information. Predictive ability is also an extremely important listening micro skill. In everyday communication, people continually make unconscious predictions about what speakers will say, and these predictions are made on the basis of their knowledge of the context in which the communication is made. The development of predictive ability has many aspects. Before listening training, teachers might ask students' questions related to listening materials or introduce relevant background knowledge to enlighten students 'thinking to allow students a clear recognition of the goals and requirements of listening training. The ability to guess the meaning of words is also an important listening micro skill. Listening comprehension does not mean understanding every word, but some words do play a crucial part in listening comprehension. It is a normal phenomenon not to understand every word that is uttered. However, students may guess the meaning of new words on the basis of the topic being discussed and gain some understanding of the probable linguistic items on the basis of the context of discourses, the grammatical structure and the background knowledge of the topic.

2.11.2 Textbook-based Learning and Other Listening Contexts

Listening lessons require listeners to concentrate on the content and make fast responses to what is heard. If students are passive and apprehensive during listening training, they will probably feel nervous and wary of taking chances. Teachers need to take a non-punitive approach and structure lessons that are varied, vivid and interesting. Teachers need to select a wide range of materials to increase listening content besides using textbooks. Students need to listen to

different levels of English in order to be exposed to natural, lively, rich language, such as listening to English songs, seeing films with English text. In these ways it is possible to raise students' enthusiasm, cultivate their listening interests, and achieve the goals of learning English.

2.11.3 Passing on Cultural Knowledge in Language Teaching

Understanding that language is controlled by particular cultural experiences is a necessity for the language learner. If the cultural differences between the students' own culture and that of the language they are to learn is excessive, learners will usually keep some distance from the target language in their efforts to maintain their psychological comfort level. As a consequence, the operating processes of memory and input will certainly be limited (Cheng Huaiyuan, 1999). Thus, teachers need to be aware that breaking down the barriers is a significant part of cultural teaching and forms an important aspect of the whole process of language teaching. The aspect of cultural knowledge transmission is an equal part of language improvement and development of work in listening development has the potential for achieving a powerful influence on the formulation of students' thinking habits and the application of foreign language expressions. Cultural teaching, then, has direct and concrete influences on intercultural communication. When students gain an intimate knowledge of the culture of the target language, they begin to understand how the language is used to reflect the thoughts, behaviors and customs of that society. In teaching English listening, teachers need to develop students' consciousness about intercultural communication and they need to energize students' capacity for wanting to engage with a different culture. Great care needs to be taken when selecting listening material and auxiliary texts, since these are a crucial aspect of the cultural factors in listening teaching. The selection of material related to British and American cultural background knowledge is of

particular importance, since these tend to be the focus of much of the classroom time when students 'thinking ability and intercultural awareness is being cultivated.

2.11.4 Combining “Intensive Listening” with “Extensive Listening”; Focusing on Listening

Intensive listening requires students to understand the meaning of each discourse and, ultimately, to understand every sentence and word. Generally, intensive listening requires students to listen to a text several times, or divide the text into paragraphs and sentences to understand each one; or by doing dictation word by word. The goal is for students to understand every sentence. Alternatively, extensive listening does not require students to understand every sentence, and every word, instead, students are encouraged to grasp the general meaning of the passage. The key point of listening is to understand the content. The purpose of intensive listening is to build basic listening skills, while extensive listening is to strengthen and enlarge effectiveness of intensive listening in order to improve overall listening ability. In listening teaching, both intensive and extensive listening should be combined with cultivating students' basic skills, the development of the productive listening habits of active thinking and the ability to understand the text. Therefore, teachers must encourage students to engage in intensive listening in class, requiring students to understand the general meaning and also to become familiarized with English pronunciation, intonation and the changes in language flow. In activities outside the class students need to engage in extensive listening; listening to many different variety of language phenomena and gaining more knowledge through TV programs, radio, the Internet and as many other kinds of exposure to listening training they can find. Exposure to demands of listening should include aspects of everyday life, science and technology, and academic lectures. Teachers must create language-learning environments that stimulate students 'interests and raise students 'passion and enthusiasm for learning English.

2.11.5 Combining Listening with Other Skills

According to language acquisition theory, human capacity for discrimination between language intention and language content is a crucial step in the language acquisition process. Thus, listening comprehensive ability plays an important role in acquisition and improvement of language skills. Therefore, in listening teaching, there is a need to combine the development of listening ability with the development of other skills such as reading. In order to improve listening ability it is necessary to listen frequently to a teacher reading well, since it is very difficult to generate a high-quality output without appropriate input. Secondly, students need to practice reading aloud among themselves. Through such activity students will learn to combine the act of listening with reading. Students must be actively engaged in producing language of high quality if they are to improve their English proficiency levels. Similarly, by combining listening with writing, teachers can divide the work into two parts. First, students might answer teachers' questions in written English after listening to spoken language material. It is also important to remember that good listening entails recalling the essence of the material rather than the precise detail. Thirdly, teachers should combine listening activities with speaking in ways that bring out the basics of oral communication. Inevitably, listeners will lose the information resources without speaking; speaking will lose its objective without careful listening and, as a result, speaking ability will not be acquired. Listening and speaking relies on each other and regulates each other. It is important to strengthen listening through speaking and to improve speaking through listening. Students need to retell and discuss the material they have just heard in order to synthesize their understanding. In this way they learn to combine listening with speaking properly. Students who can do this are able to overcome their passive response to the

situation and gradually they learn to feel safe when they respond. In order for this to happen, a truly interactive and penalty-free listening class is required.

Teacher/student and students/student exchanges should be emphasized as opportunities for a free exchange of opinions when participants can consolidate their listening approaches and skills during the process of communication. Through a variety of listening-reading, listening-writing and listening-speaking activities, students can not only strengthen their language skills but also sharpen their interests and raise their motivation to improve their learning efficiency.

2.12 Teaching Listening Activities

Listening is a highly-complex solving activities (Barnes, 1984) in which listeners interact with a speaker to construct meaning, within the context of their experiences and knowledge. When students are made aware of the factors that affect listening, the levels of listening, and the components of the listening process, they are more likely to recognize their own listening abilities and engage in activities that prepare them to be effective listeners. Karakas (2002) states that listening activities try to prevent failure so that they can support the learner's interpretation of the text. Listening activities are usually subcategorized as pre-listening, while-listening, and post-listening activities.

2.12.1 A. Pre-listening Activities

Schema theory provides strong evidence for the effectiveness of pre-listening activities which includes the outline for listening to the text and teaching cultural key concepts. Listening teacher may select certain words, difficult grammatical structures and expressions to be explained through the discussion about the topic and may also ask students to predict the content or what speakers are going to say, based on the information they have already got. Pre-listening activities

usually have two primary goals: (a) to help to activate students' prior knowledge, build up their expectations for the coming information; and (b) to provide the necessary context for the specific listening task. The teacher could follow with a listening comprehension activity, such as two people having a conversation about their daily life. Students must answer true or false questions based on the previous listening activity. An example of a controlled practice activity could be a drill activity that models the same structure or vocabulary (Karakas, 2002).

2.12.2 While-listening Activities

Listeners who participate actively in the listening experience are more likely to construct clear and accurate meaning as they interpret the speaker's verbal message and nonverbal cues. During the listening experience students verify and revise their predictions. They make interpretations and judgments based on what they heard. Listening teacher may ask students to note down key words to work out the main points of the text. Students answer comprehension questions while listening to the text and select specific information to complete the table provided with the text. While-listening activities usually have some of the following purposes: to focus students' understanding of the speaker's language and ideas; to focus students' attention on such things as the speaker's organizational patterns; to encourage students' critical reactions and personal responses to the speaker's ideas and use of language. An open-ended activity could follow that allows students to have the freedom to practice listening comprehension in the class about their daily life and asking for further information. Listening comprehension should begin with what students already know so that they can build on their existing knowledge and skills with activities designed on the same principle. A variation on the filling in the missing word listening activity could be to use the same listening materials, but to set a pair work activity

where student A and student B have the same worksheet where some information items are missing (Karakas, 2002).

2.12.3 Post-listening Activities

Post-listening activities are important because they extend students' listening skills. Post-listening activities are most effective when done immediately after the listening experience. Well-planned post-listening activities offer students opportunities to connect what they have heard to their own ideas and experiences and encourage interpretive and critical listening and reflective thinking. As well, post-listening activities provide opportunities for teachers to assess and check students' comprehension and clarify their understanding; to extend comprehension beyond the literal level to the interpretive and critical levels. Different comprehension questions can be assigned for students to discuss after listening, students then swap information to complete the whole class chart, correlating what each student has heard to arrive at the big picture. If there are any questions that remain unanswered during the first or second listening, and after the information swap activity, the whole class can listen to the tape again. The students will then try to find the answer to the questions that have not been previously understood, rather than the teacher providing the answers straight away (Karakas, 2002).

2.13 Current Focus on Listening Research

This section briefly describes where listening research is concentrated today. Rubin (1994) stated that much of current research on listening has been devoted to the factors that may influence second/foreign language listening comprehension. According to Rubin, the five major factors are as follows: text characteristics (variation in a listening passage/text or associated visual support); interlocutor characteristics (variation in the speaker's personal characteristics); task characteristics (variation in the purpose for listening and associated responses); listener

characteristics (variation in the listener's personal characteristics); and finally, process characteristics (variation in the listener's cognitive activities and in the nature of the interaction between the speaker and listener).

Peterson (2001) pointed out that future research on listening should concentrate on students' proficiency levels and strategy use, saying that "we need to know more about what good listeners do and how they learn their strategies" (p. 98). She also suggested that we need to know more about the effects of more intensive classroom practices on bottom-up as well as topdown processing. Finally, Peterson (2001) and Duker (1964) agreed that there is a need for more commonly accepted measures of proficiency in SL/FL listening. They argued that this area has been neglected, and that much research needs to be done. In other words, it is necessary to create assessments that serve as standards in listening comprehension.

Additionally, today's research on listening assessment points to the need to address the importance of visuals in the making of better listening comprehension tests. For example, Buck (2001) indicated that visual information is an important variable in language comprehension because it helps define the context in which the spoken message will be interpreted. He added that "the common practice of playing a disembodied recording from an audio player does not create a very realistic listening situation" (p. 253). However, he argued that because technologies such as videotapes, cameras, and video players have become available for providing visual information in class, it is also necessary to know how this visual technology affects listening comprehension; because visual information may sometimes interfere with the testing processes, it may increase what Buck called "the cognitive load" of the test taker. He concluded, then, that research is necessary to explore testing with visuals, with no visuals, with still pictures, and so

on. Buck also called for research on what happens when the visual information conflicts with the verbal information.

Theoretical Approaches Related to Visually Supported Listening Schema Theory and L2 Listening Comprehension.

Listening is primarily a cognitive activity, involving the activation and modification of concepts in the listener's mind. As a way of referring to activated portions of conceptual knowledge, cognitive psychologists and linguists often refer to modules of knowledge as schemas (or schemata). For example, if you are listening to a news broadcast on an international conflict in Colombia, you might bring to mind numerous existing schemas about drugs, kidnapping and violence, and history in this country. Indeed, according to Rost (2002), you will need to bring them into your memory in order to comprehend any news story.

Because comprehension involves the formation of meaning in our minds, our knowledge of the world needs to be utilized in the comprehension process. That is why cognitive researchers stated that human knowledge is organized around schemata or banks of information that people bring to mind. This theory plays an important role in reading as well as in listening comprehension. Regarding listening, schema theory allows students to construct meaning by supplying relevant background knowledge in the process of comprehension rather than by only matching the sound and meaning. In other words students might be able to make associations between what they are hearing and what they know about the topic or theme of a conversation, and in this way they might be able to predict, anticipate, or confirm what is to be heard in the upcoming listening activity (Samuels, 1984). To this end, the use of VEPP before and during listening activities may play a positive role in the activation of listeners' background knowledge and in the comprehension process.

According to different researchers (Bacon,1992 ;Cook,1996; Teng, 1997), the use of schemata in listening comprehension is an advantage for second language learners because, first, at lower levels of language learning, students with limited or no background knowledge might have to rely solely on the imperfect or null L2 linguistics knowledge to decode the listening passage. Therefore, visual techniques (such as VEPP) and strategies for schemata activation might play a positive role for these language learners at this particular level. Second, another advantage of using schemata activation is that learners possess "scripts" (versions, models, and patterns of different real-life conversations) that might be helpful in making inferential and listening processes much easier and more accurate. Additionally, if students are aware of the situational and cultural background knowledge of the listening passages, they are about to hear, their comprehension could be also enhanced. Thus, activation of schemata turns out to be an important goal for language instructors in their instructional setting. In conclusion, schema theory implies that if L2 learners are induced to use their background know ledge in comprehension, this can override the difficulty they may have in dealing with linguistic aspects of any conversation.

2.14 Internet-Based Instructions Vs Traditional Instructions

Nowadays, many internet-based and online instructions and courses are in process and the number of students interested in such instructions is growing (Bryan & Hegelheimer, 2007). Even distance education has grown fast in recent years. Until now the benefits of using internet and online instruction was not known. On one hand, Clark (1985) maintained that media do not influence learning in any condition. On the other hand, Liu (2008) debated that educational

technologies influence learning by interacting with an individual 's cognitive and social processes in constructing knowledge.

With online instruction, the student is separated from the teacher and connected through the use of a computer and the Internet. More and more institutions are offering online courses and/or programs to their students in order to meet various learners 'needs. Online learning and instruction, as an integral part of the teaching and learning process in higher education, is growing as fast as the technology itself. On the other hand, conventional classroom instruction is face-to-face instruction, typically conducted in a classroom setting in a lecture/discussion/note taking mode.

Kearsley (1995) found that some benefits of online courses include increased student satisfaction, better examination scores, and a higher level of critical thinking. Other cited benefits of internet-based instruction are user-friendliness, self-paced learning and 24-hour access. With regard to information retention, Barth (1990) found that interactive multimedia computer lessons resulted in an 80 per cent retention rate, while lecture and associated visuals resulted in a mere 20 per cent retention rate in a sample of students. Other studies have found that computer-assisted instruction allows teachers to deliver the same material in a shorter period of time (Jain & Getis, 2003, p. 2).

The advancement of the Internet has created new ways of learning and teaching English as a second/foreign Language (ESL/EFL). For instance, the Internet can be considered as an ideal learning and teaching tool because it offers authentic learning resources available.

2.15 A historical overview on technology-aided learning strategy

A few years ago, there was a prediction that mobile technologies in many parts of the world, specifically in the UK, would become a natural and necessary part for the majority of both teachers and students (Kukulska-Hulme & Shield, 2008). Moreover, a quick review of mobile learning projects (m-learning) in Europe indicates the application of mobiles in many contexts according to Pechrzewska and Knot (2007). According to Kukulska-Hulme and Shield (2008), mobile learning is the use of any portable learning materials such as audio CDs and DVD players and “m-learning usually concentrates on the most recent technologies” (p.273). Likewise, Trifanova, Knapp, Ronchetti, and Gamper (2004) have defined mobile devices as small devices that go with us almost everywhere. To conclude, Geddes (2004) mentions that m-learning can be identified by the tools which are available at any place and at any time.

2.16 A brief historical overview of technology and language learning

Usually, any act of language learning and teaching involves the use of a particular type of technology (Warschaur and Meskill, 2000). For instance, language teachers who followed the grammar translation method in which the teacher elaborated on grammatical minutiae and the learners translated sentences from the L2 into their L1 relied on the earliest type of technology, i.e. blackboard. Later on, the use of overhead projectors, as well as early software computer programs, was responsible for provision of mechanical drilling. During the 1970s, when the Audio-Lingual method was at its best, practitioners embarked on the use of audio-taped materials, which required obligatory trips to audio labs where students had to repeat monotonous pattern drills. By the late 1970s, due to incapability of language learners in responding to unrehearsed situations, the Audio-Lingual method fell out of favor. Seen in another light, this method waned in popularity due to its lack of focus on communicative aspects of language use.

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, due to the emergence of cognitive and sociolinguistic approaches to language teaching along with an emphasis on student engagement with authentic, meaningful and contextualized discourse, there was a full-scale shift in the use of technology in the classrooms.

2.17 Cognitive approaches

Cognitive approaches tend to view learning as a psychological process through which learners strive for making a mental model of language system through active interactions of cognitive structures and comprehensible input (Chastain 1988). Therefore, errors are not seen as signs of bad habits which must be avoided but rather as natural by-products of this construction process. Technologies which are resonant with cognitive approaches are those which allow learners to have maximum opportunity of interaction within meaning-rich contexts so that learners can foster competence. Some of these technologies are text-reconstruction, concordance, telecommunications and multimedia simulation software.

Text-reconstruction software such as NewReader or TextTanagers from research design association gives learners an opportunity to either put in the letters that are missing or arrange them in the right order. Concordancing software (e.g. Monoconc) allows learners to search through either small or large texts to see instances of real language use of some words. In this way, it acts as a fruitful supplement to dictionaries. Multimedia simulation software allows learners to enter into a so called "linguistic bath" environment to experience culture first. Examples include *A la rencontre de Philippe* developed by the Athena Language Learning Project at MIT Laboratory for Advanced Technology in the Humanities. *Philippe*, a game for intermediate and advanced French learners, incorporates full motion video, sound, graphics, and

text, allowing learners to explore simulated environments by following street signs or floor plans (Warschaur and Meskill 2000).

2.18 Sociolinguistic approaches

These approaches see socialization and working with people as indispensable aspects of any act of language learning and teaching. Hence, learning a language is viewed as a process of apprenticeship or socialization into particular discourse communities (Schieffelin and Ochs 1986). From this perspective students need to be given opportunities to practice social aspects not only to understand comprehensible input but also to be engaged in activities that are focused on developing output (Mackey 2007). This can be achieved through student collaboration on authentic tasks and projects (Prabhu 1987; Willis and Willis 2007) while simultaneously learning both content and language (Flowerdew 1993; Snow 1991). From this perspective the Internet is a type of technology which can be used in a myriad of ways in any act of teaching/learning. This, for example, can be achieved through computer-mediated communication for long-distance exchange by means of e-mail and web-based conferencing systems (Warschaur and Meskill 2000), which is particularly useful in settings where students have limited opportunities for authentic target language use.

2.19 Mobile assisted language learning strategy

As mentioned earlier, with the emergence of different methods there has always been a recurrent use of different forms of technology. For instance, the espousal of the Audio-Lingual method brought about an enormous focus on language laboratories, which gradually became the fashion of the day (Salaberry 2001). Influenced by behaviorism, the language laboratories were equipped by drill-based computer assisted instruction in the 1960s, which then was progressively replaced by a more intelligent approach namely, computer assisted language learning (CALL) in

the 1990s. As technologies continue to be used more extensively in teaching and learning settings, so does their propensity to shrink in size. "Other technologies that hold capacity for language learning include PDA, multimedia cellular phones, MP3 players, DVD players and digital dictionaries" (Zhao 2005, p.447).

As with other forms of technology, mobile assisted language learning (MALL) is a branch of technology-enhanced learning which can be implemented in numerous forms including face-to-face, distant or on-line modes. However, different scholars in the field have underscored that MALL should be implemented in the classroom, taking the presence of learners as a paramount factor into consideration. As Colpaert (2004) has rightly argued, before using mobile technologies a learning environment should be fostered. Likewise, Salaberry (2001) has argued against "technology- driven pedagogy" emphasizing the fact that despite their considerable benefits nothing to date has proved that any type of technology can necessarily act better than traditional forms of teaching. Finally, as Beatty (2003) has asserted, "Teachers need to be concerned about investigating time and money in unproven technology" (p.72). All in all, using any kind of technological device should be accompanied by developing an efficacious type of methodology because these devices are not instructors but rather instructional tools.

2.20 Research study on the effectiveness of M-learning

In an attempt to study whether mobile phones were useful learning tools, Kiernan and Aizawa (2004) explored their utility in task-based learning. They argued that second language acquisition is best promoted through utilization of tasks, which require learners to bridge some sort of gap, thereby focusing their attention on meaning. In the traditional classroom, however, such activities are easily defeated by the close proximity of students. The use of mobile technologies would be one way to separate learners. In their study, upper and lower proficiency

level Japanese university students were placed in three groups; PC mail users, mobile phone email users, and mobile phone speaking users (due to cost the latter group became face to face speaking users). They were given a pretest, three narrative tasks, three invitation tasks and a repeated posttest. The results generally showed that the face to face groups were superior in terms of communicative performance in comparison to the other two groups.

There were three more studies in Japan, which examined the use of cell phones in education (Thornton and Houser, 2005). In these studies students were surveyed regarding their use of mobile phones. English vocabulary lessons were sent to the learners' mobile phones using short text messages and a website was developed to explain the English idioms which students surfed using the 3G phones. The findings revealed that mobile phones are ubiquitous among students and learners were ready to read small texts on mobile screens. It was noted that mobile phones can effectively serve to educate a foreign language learner and short text messages is very useful in teaching vocabulary. One of these studies was made to investigate the use of short text messages for group discussions in school and business meetings. Text messages were received from the audience, stored in database and later displayed on the computer screen as posted notes. Presenters read these messages and gave feedback to the audience. It was found that this method can help those who are reluctant to ask questions due to their shyness. In a recent study, Sole, Calic, and Neijmann (2010) showed that mobiles can allow learners to express themselves in a variety of scenarios. This study included two case studies and was conducted over two years in one of the UK universities. Students were required to report on their work with mobile devices outside the classroom. It was shown that using mobile devices help learners have a better engagement with learning and to have a better interaction. The results also showed that mobile devices also facilitate contextual learning and they resultantly allow the

information to be captured in learner's own location in a way as to be resonant with students' needs.

In the MALL Research Project Report (2009), it was concluded that mobile phones have a considerable effect on boosting students' confidence in both listening and speaking. In this study, a group of students was asked to have some conversation in Indonesian on their mobile phones. The results obtained showed that all students were satisfied with the privacy and freedom that they had using their own mobile devices. Moreover, the teachers welcomed the facility of listening to their students' conversations because they could identify each student's difficulty better. In this study, students undertook a conversation test at the beginning of the project to quantify their initial conversational ability and a post-test to realize their progress. An 11% increase in their mean score from the pretest to the posttest showed the great effect that mobiles can have on improving language ability.

Finally, at the University of Lancaster, Mitchell, Race, McCaffery, Bryson, and Cai's (2006) study involved using short text messages as a way to make communications between teachers and students possible. They found that text messaging is a cost-effective mechanism to convey the personalized information to learners' mobile phones in a trendy fashion.

2.21. Crossing onto the Banks of the Digital World

Listening comprehension activities are more multisensory and interactive than ever. With advances in technology and instructional design, the computer can now provide sight, sound, and text to enhance students' aural comprehension, all within the confines of a single piece of equipment. How this has evolved over the last two decades has been closely tied to the digital and pedagogical evolution and greater focus on second language acquisition. Numerous research

studies have examined the varying ways that these new digital technologies can enhance aural comprehension and have often highlighted the benefits of interactive computer-based activities. Yet, as we cross the bridge from analog to digital, core questions come to mind regarding digital technologies and aural comprehension. Can we reassure ourselves that when we step onto the banks of the digital world the ground will be solid? Let us briefly examine several questions that have been addressed in the last decade or so to better understand the significance of and instill confidence in this ever-evolving digital world.

2.22. Listening Comprehension and Technology: On the Banks of the Analog River

During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the typical approach to language learning entailed reading and writing in a foreign language, learning grammatical rules, memorizing word lists, and completing “errorless” translations. At this same time, precursors of today’s technology emerged in the form of wax cylinders and 78 records onto which one could permanently record words and songs. Despite the birth of this innovative technology, its use for language learning was out of curiosity at best, limited to the preservation of actively dying indigenous languages.

After World War II, the primary way to develop aural comprehension was to maintain a structural analysis of the language and to provide students with several hours of drill per day, in small classes, with the help of a native speaker (Bloomfield, 1942).

Educators began to react against such labor-intensive strategies and, with time, cylinders and 78 records evolved into LPs and reel-to-reel tapes, new technologies that immediately found a home in the audiolingual method (ALM). This new teaching style approached language acquisition as a behavioristic process and emphasized habit formation and stimulus response activities as steppingstones to language acquisition. The new reel-to-reel technology seemed like

a good fit for language learning but yet was very elusive; no one knew how to use it well (Rubrecht, 1977) with some suggesting that tapes were “miracle drugs: in order to be effective, they must be made by experts, prescribed by experts, and administered by experts” (Harris, 1961, p. 465). Thus, despite the “newness” of technology and its application to language learning, listening comprehension was soon labeled a “long-neglected area” (Rivers, 1966, p. 196). In response, language labs were developed to serve as the ideal technological means to model and reinforce students’ aural conditioning and verbal responses. The belief was that language lab technology could help students hear difficult sounds and sound sequences and could support individualized learning. Depending upon the setup of the lab, students could control their audio input, and teachers could leave to the lab and its monitors all the drudgery of drill and pattern practice while keeping for themselves the interesting aspects of language learning. Holec and Kuhn (1971) reinforced the lab’s usefulness for intermediate and advanced study suggesting that reading tapes would provide comprehension exercises and conversation preparation for in-class activities, thereby making the “lonely lab” less of a drudgery than typically perceived (Chvany, 1972). However, audiotaped material in general was viewed as nonauthentic, boring, and irrelevant, and, prior to the development of published listening comprehension materials, aural lessons had to be written and recorded by the teachers themselves (Rubrecht, 1977). As a result, teachers ignored what happened in the lab and students often turned down the volume to study for other classes; little motivation was present (Quinn, 1975).

Complaints soon emerged regarding the speed of the aural material. The technology world responded and developed speech compressors and expanders to adjust the speed of the audio without affecting the pitch of the speaker and to alleviate cognitive overload in short term memory (Harvey, 1978). Studies soon followed to examine the impact of slowed speech on aural

comprehension (i.e., Harvey, 1984; Nord, 1975; Smith, 1980). Smith (1980) had students listen to an aural text at a rate of 20% less than the normal rate, 10% less than the normal rate, and then at a normal rate. He found that a slower rate was not helpful in comprehending aural material. Flaherty (1975), however, found that French students performed better on aural comprehension tests when the rate of the aural text was expanded to 135%; expansion to 170%, a much slower pace, did not increase comprehension.

Speed aside, there was little creativity within the lab and technological problems emerged such as broken machines, displaced knobs, twisted tapes, and cramped space. Little evidence suggested that aural activities helped students to learn a language. Interest was precarious at best with some even developing mathematical formulas to analyze students' motivation towards aural materials: "Success is a function of intensity of involvement multiplied by time (zero intensity input x 50 lessons = zero success)" (Rubrecht, 1977, p. 8). Language lab materials were only as good as the prerecorded tape, and little to no interaction was present; the goal was simply to identify sounds and to develop flawless linguistic patterns (i.e., Field, 1998; Pill, 1971; Postovsky, 1981; Richard-Amato, 1996). Yet, rumblings of a not-too-distant drum could be heard. Severin (1967) found that processing an aural text with pictures led to greater results on posttreatment activities than did processing the same aural text with sound only, or sound and unrelated images. Severin's research findings were prophetic for the multimedia we now know today. With time, ALM evolved into other teaching methods: the direct method stressed repetition of language components and focused on grammar as the topic of discussion (Richard-Amato, 1996); the natural approach also stressed comprehension before speaking but, in addition, emphasized short responses to questions that lengthened with time (Richard-Amato, 1996; Terrell, 1977); total physical response (TPR) emphasized comprehension before speaking

and required students to listen and respond physically (through actions or gestures) to the aural information (Asher, 1969; Asher, Jusudo, & de la Torre, 1974; Richard-Amato, 1996). In terms of research, Kalivoda, Morain, and Elkins (1971) examined the use of 10-minute audiotaped TPR activities structured around themes with students listening and responding physically as teachers acted out the language clues. Students stated that such a strategy increased their aural and vocabulary comprehension and that it was a stimulating change of pace.

Despite such efforts to help students develop their language skills, educators generally did not take time to examine more appropriate uses of technology. As listen-and-repeat strategies droned on, meaningful communication through interaction was deemed essential if students were to acquire and use a language (Chanier, 1994). This demanded modernization and rejuvenation of the language lab, with special attention to more interactive and interesting recorded materials and technologies. The students themselves, their learning styles, their prior knowledge of and attitudes toward the language, along with the presentation of the audio materials, would also need to be addressed to explore how listening comprehension activities could best enhance students' aural development (Cullen, 1975). Soon, researchers began to examine such factors as language proficiency and material design in their research. For example, Mueller (1980) factored student proficiency levels into his examination of how an aural passage with visual material might affect students' success with listening comprehension activities. He asked students at different proficiency levels to review an aural passage in three separate manners: listening only, listening with images simultaneously presented, and listening with images presented after the passage. He determined that high proficiency learners could successfully process aural information alone but that lower proficiency level learners needed support, in the form of simultaneously presented pictures and sound, to best process the aural information. This finding

revealed that a relationship exists among students' characteristics, their language-learning strategies, and the manner in which the information is presented to them (Carlson, 1990).

Students who are proficient may not need to rely on visual aids as much since they can generate analogical representations as they listen; mainly inexperienced students benefit most from pictures coordinated with words (Mayer & Sims, 1994). All that was now needed was for educators to build a bridge towards technological and pedagogical strategies that could soundly coordinate aural, visual, and text-based information along with learners' needs and differences to enhance aural comprehension. Such a scenario was just over the horizon.

2.23. Listening Comprehension: Crossing the Bridge from Analog to Digital

In the late 1970s and early 1980s, the communicative approach to language teaching emphasized a more active use of language to perform tasks based on meaning, not form. This method, in use today, is more tolerant of errors and deemphasizes exercises that focus strictly on grammar-based, drill-and-practice strategies. Students learn to communicate socially and competently in the target language; teachers make extensive use of audio-visual technologies and employ pre-listening activities and subsequent listening and inferential activities when working with aural texts (Field, 1998; Stone, 1988). Educators also use more authentic recordings than previous methods and stress the importance of inferring meaning from a difficult passage. Thus, the focus is no longer on discrete units of language, unrelated words or expressions out of context, but rather lengthier chunks of discourse and active negotiation with others in situations that have substance and meaning (Chanier, 1994; Hoven, 1999; Meskill, 1996).

In the early stages of the communicative approach, new strategies in the design and development of audio and videotaped educational materials quickly emerged. In terms of the

language lab, Stone (1988) published a manual that emphasized the creative, communicative use of lab equipment and materials for aural comprehension activities. This text provided numerous examples of activities that entailed aural communication based on themes, not grammatical repetition. At the same time, the desktop computer was just becoming readily available and educators began to build bridges between computers, analog tape, and language study (i.e., Stevens, 1983; Webb, 1985). Mydlarski and Paramskas (1985) developed “Dictate,” a template to help students practice aural comprehension through dictation tasks. The software would highlight errors and students in turn would discern how they wished to proceed with error correction; the audio was delivered by tape. Soon, technology supported the connection of computers to tape players to allow random access of audio segments on the tape (Henry, 1987). In particular, MacLang (Frommer, 1990) brought more interactive top-down and bottom-up activities to the aural comprehension forefront. With this software, one could create basic lessons that included fill-in-the-blank, multiple-choice and word-ordering activities and immediate feedback. Beginning and ending points would be programmed into the software allowing the computer to control access to segments of the audiotape using the interfaced audio tape player. The MacLang program was easy to use, allowed faculty to develop activities that coincided with their syllabuses, and made listening more active and less linear (Frommer, 1989). And yet, a prominent drawback to this interfaced system was that the audiotape would stretch, get out of synchronization with the computer, or break. Around this same time, Barrutia (1985) “called” on CALL to find ways to incorporate digitized speech into a computer. Fischer (1986) responded and examined the potential of the “Victor 9000 computer” for supporting listening comprehension. This computer allowed for easy recording, storage, and playback of speech with the sound quality comparable to that of a tape player. Technology was now providing “a

benchmark, a notion of what we should demand...when we contemplate how the computer can, or might, or should serve our purposes as teachers of language for practical proficiency”

(Fischer, 1986, p. 31).

With a new transition underway, researchers turned to comparison studies of computer-driven activities to audiocassette, paper-and-pencil activities. Shiu and Smaldino (1993) compared audiotape materials and computer-based materials in the Chinese language. Students were asked to listen to an aural dialogue and to answer follow-up questions. While there were no noticeable differences on aural comprehension tests, students preferred the quality of the computer-based audio activities over audiotape activities. Balizet, Treder, and Parshall (1999) later examined how a computer-delivered listening comprehension text and an audiocassette/paper-and-pencil test might differ in their impact on sound quality, convenience, and aural comprehension. No significant differences were found on English as a Second Language (ESL) comprehension tests for the audiotape and computer-based audio modules. However, students again indicated that the computer's sound quality was much improved over the cassette tape, and the ability to more precisely control the audio text was a plus. Coniam (1996) wanted to see how a computer program could help students work alone with listening comprehension to develop ESL proficiency. The program dictated a text to students who, in turn, entered components of the dictation into the computer. The findings suggested that the computer-based dictation was just as effective as in-class, written dictations.

Thus, one transition was complete; computers now could handle audio and text simultaneously and effectively. However, concerns were raised that if students' internal knowledge structures were low, aural comprehension would be an insurmountable task even for the best of students (Wolff, 1987). Fortunately, researchers began to address the question of how

students could process sensory information including text and auditory material to enhance aural comprehension in ways other than through pure dictation. Jakobsaottir and Hooper (1995) examined a TPR approach that used computer icons, graphics, and text to help students respond to spoken commands in Norwegian. They found that presenting an aural component with text helped students to develop their aural skills; students showed greater motivation, greater confidence, and greater understanding than when text was absent. Such an outcome suggests that when prior knowledge of aural material is low, it makes sense to provide visual and text-based information that supports and extends the listening comprehension process (Garza, 1991). Audio alone may be sufficient for those with prior knowledge of a particular topic, but presentation of an aural component coordinated with visual and verbal symbol systems could help those less knowledgeable with the material to enhance their aural comprehension (Kozma, 1991).

With the successful combination of computers and digitized audio established, some suggested that each learner would eventually own not a tape player but a computer interfaced with a videodisc player and television (Leveridge, 1979), that such equipment would bring more individuality to the education system (Bork, 1981), and that audio materials would make regular use of authentic speech (Harvey, 1984). This new emphasis on language teaching and audio technology soon included interaction between students and fast nonlinear retrieval of audio-visual information (Joy, Lian, & Russell, 1983). Stevens (1983) examined the use of an “apple II+ computer interfaced with a SONY SL-323 Betamax video cassette recorder (VCR) using a Gentech ETS-2000 controller” (p. 27) to see how well the interfaced equipment would work and how user friendly it would be. Stevens found that this new technology demanded a large commitment of time and resources that many were not yet prepared to give. Nevertheless, he correctly hypothesized that interactive video discs, not video tape, would soon play a prominent

role in language learning, primarily because of the ability of videodisc to accurately display a video segment. For example, Kim (1987) combined interactive videodisc and computer technologies to enhance listening comprehension in Korean using options such as feedback, translation, cultural notes, vocabulary, and grammar cues to support students' different backgrounds, language levels, and learning strategies. As interest in videodisc technology continued to rise, numerous individuals and organizations such as the Project for International Communication Studies (PICS) developed videodiscs with authentic materials to provide high quality audio and video components to students (Hughes, 1993; Knisbacher, 1991; Whiskeyman, 1990). Thus, the use of authentic texts took off with the belief that such material could help learners overcome cultural barriers to language learning (Bacon & Finnemann, 1990) and that early exposure to such texts would help students better comprehend more difficult texts later on (Bacon, 1989, 1992). Bacon (1989) argued that barring beginning language learners from the natural language would prevent them from interacting with others effectively. Faerch and Kaspar (1986) further stressed that interaction was needed to help students develop meaning from a text. Hendricks (1994) examined the use of interactive instructional design models to support a movement away from linear processing. He found that with the increase in interactivity, technology could now easily provide helpful components such as transcriptions, dictionaries, glossaries, pictures, testing resources, grammar checks, and so on, as well as video control capabilities. Students could also interact with activities that would vary their experiences based on their responses to questions. With the adventure program *Montevidisco* (Larson & Bush, 1992), students could "visit" a Mexican town and encounter thematic situations and vary their experiences all with the help of interactive tools.

To help teachers develop their own interactive lessons, numerous educators created educational authoring software. Otto and Pusack (1992) developed The Listening Tool, an application that allows students to explore authentic L2 video material with helpful comprehension aids. Farris and Fischer (1994) followed with Libra, a multimedia tool with which teachers could develop interactive computer-based L2 activities for their students complete with pictures, sound, and connections to videodisc technologies. Using Libra and the videodisc “La Marée et Ses Secrets” (Russell & Cottave, 1989), Fischer (1996) examined the effects of the presence or absence of multimedia components such as vocabulary or character introduction, narrative structure analysis, and multiple forms of follow-up activities such as checklist questions, icon-sorting questions, and multiple-choice questions on students’ aural comprehension. He found that the instructional design had a significant impact on students’ listening comprehension; those students who could work with multimedia components that took advantage of sound pedagogical approaches to learning (e.g., advance organizers and supportive questions) outperformed those students who had few multimedia options available to them. His study suggests that students are most likely to learn when sound pedagogical strategies are incorporated into multimedia-based lessons.

Publishing companies also jumped onto the videodisc bandwagon. A videodisc entitled Blickkontakte (Pusack & Tschirner, 1996) was produced for Kontakte (Terrell, 1996), a communicative-based German text which emphasizes listening comprehension. Pusack (1999) explored how software could contribute to a learner’s self-directed learning from the videodisc by offering, among other things, aural comprehension practice. Interactive multimedia lessons using the Dasher Authoring System (Pusack & Otto, 1992) were created to offer pre-, during and postviewing support and to provide both small and large chunks of language; such a strategy

allowed students to control the material more easily. Pusack's (1999) work raised the question of whether or not one could ever create a fully comprehensive multimedia textbook. He suggested that such a product was possible but would have to be a continuous work-in-progress, updated constantly indicating that "the effort to provide maximum multimedia support for a major textbook ... has no true beginning or end" (p. 40). It would not be long before Pusack's dream would become a reality (University of Texas, 2004).

With computers and videodisc capabilities in full force, research soon examined the impact of these technologies on students' aural comprehension. Chang and Smith (1991) examined how collaboration at an interactive videodisc activity might affect students' aural comprehension. They found that students who worked together enhanced their ability to respond to implicit or thought-provoking questions, but that collaborative learning did not have an impact, positive or negative, on responding to factual questions. Brett (1997) compared students' performance on aural comprehension exercises when working with audiotape, videotape, or multimedia-based technologies. He found that students were most successful when working with multimedia, primarily because of the instant feedback they received from the available technology.

Though multimodal materials in aural comprehension activities were found to enhance students' learning, not all researchers supported their use in listening comprehension. MacWilliam (1986) believed that dually coded information hindered listening comprehension because it placed too many demands on students and could lead to a potential loss of information. Though Pouwels (1992) supported identifying and addressing learners' needs, he found that students who were more strongly attuned to processing information aurally were quite distracted by simultaneously presented visual and verbal information; this combination led to a

significant decrease in comprehension. These two studies suggested that providing an inappropriate amount or combination of information could split students' attention and prevent them from learning (Sweller, 1994). Students therefore needed a technology that would allow them to choose their own learning strategy and that would give them the freedom to move around to other parts of a lesson in order to find the information that will enable understanding to go over the material in different orders—and thus in different contexts—to see the relationships among the parts (McGrath, 1992, p. 516) with a range of options geared to individual learning styles (Garrett, 1988, p. 9).

Thus, a technological tool solidly grounded in good instructional design would most help students obtain additional relevant verbal and nonverbal (visual) information. Once again, change was on the horizon and video disc technology would soon bow to the stand alone desktop computer and the internet, the newest member of the aural comprehension world.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.0 Introduction

The purpose of chapter three of our method is to describe all the procedures and practical activities to do the research. It includes detailed information about the design of the study, participants, materials, procedures, and finally, data analysis procedures.

3.1 Design of the study

This study followed quasi-experimental design. The subjects of the study were Iranian EFL learners in Zaban Iran institute in Rasht. The design of the study includes at least four stages:

1. subject selection via administering an OPT
2. exposing the participants to the pre-test of listening
3. treating the experimental group of the study with the digital proficiency and the control group with the existing method of teaching listening.
4. administering the post-test of listening to both groups of the study.

3.2 Methods

Participants: The subjects of the study were 60 Iranian EFL learners in Zaban Iran English Institute. They were selected based on the administration of an OPT exam to 100 intermediate EFL learners. Selected students received scores at least one standard deviation below the mean in the OPT. They were divided into two groups of 30 and were randomly assigned to an experimental and a control group.

3.3 Materials

The investigation was conducted using different materials. For the sake of data collection, the participants used three types of tests. An OPT test was taken in order to measure their proficiency level, and homogenize the groups, the test contains two parts. The pretest of listening was taken in order to measure learners' initial subjects' knowledge of listening. A posttest of listening was used to measure the effectiveness of treatment.

3.4 Procedure

An OPT test was prepared and administered to 100 EFL subjects. For the purpose of selecting the homogenous participants those who scored above 35 took part in the current study. After that, they were randomly divided into experimental and control groups.

Both groups sat for a pre-test of listening. The purpose of this test was to assess the initial subject knowledge of the learners in listening. Then the control group received no treatment and approached the traditional method for teaching listening and experimental group received treatment based on Digital Proficiency. In order to achieve this goal, the experimental group received treatment listening on computers online in each session. The topic which was used in this study was related to routine topics. During web discussion, every student can listen and express the input while the teacher corrects their mistakes and identify their problems, while checking their output. Another thing is that every mistake and problem of students in listening was written by the web-based teacher and next session was reviewed by the instructor.

Their classes were held once a week for 45 minutes for eight sessions. And the last step was the posttest of listening in which the subjects' ability in both groups on the specific treatment program was assessed.

3.5. Statistical analysis

The data was analyzed through measuring SPSS; an independent sample T-test was used to analyze the study.

3.6. Summary

This chapter described the procedures and practical activities to conduct the study. It includes detailed information about the design of the study, participants, materials, procedures, and finally, data analysis procedures.

Chapter 4: Analysis and Results

4.0. Introduction

In this chapter, the researcher elaborated the details of the results of study and analyzed data which has resulted in rejecting or proving the proposed hypothesis in first chapter. This chapter reports on the findings of the study and provides answers to the questions that lie at the heart of the investigation. The elaboration of the procedures of analyzing data and the support or the rejection of the hypothesis is explained in this section. The data gathered were analyzed by an Independent Sample T-test and ANCOVAs with support provided by descriptive statistics. The results of analysis are presented in forms of tables to show in a more tangible way.

4.1. Data Analysis and Findings

As was mentioned earlier in chapter 3, 60 students at a language institute took part in this survey. The much-intended goal of current study was to investigate the Effectiveness of Digital Proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners' Listening Skills. Released data from tests were calculated through ANCOVAs for elaborating the manipulation of the program which was done by implementation of different teaching methods and offering new material as treatment in experimental groups. Also, an Independent Sample T-test was used to show the degree of differences that would exist between control and experimental group. In brief it should be mentioned that after analyzing the descriptive statistics of students' listening scores on pretests and posttests, two statistical computations of the data including descriptive and inferential analysis are carried out.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis of the Data

Descriptive statistics is the discipline of quantitatively describing the main features of a collection of data. It aims to summarize a sample, rather than use the data to learn about the population that the sample data is thought to represent. Actually, it deals with analyzing, describing and interpreting the data obtained from the participants. The measures used to describe the data set are measures of central tendency and measures of variability or dispersion. Measures of central tendency include the mean, media and mode, while measures of variability include the standard deviation, the minimum and maximum variables. Descriptive analysis of the data obtained of the current study which has been calculated by SPSS is presented below.

Table 4.1. Mean, Variance and Standard Deviation of Pretests for Control and Experimental Groups					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Pretests	Control	0	10.5333	4.51613	20.395
	Experimental	0	10.6667	5.28716	27.954

Table (4.1) shows the descriptive analysis of the pretest scores of the control and the experimental group on Listening variable. Each group includes 30 participants (N=30) without any missing value (that means all selected subjects were present in the investigation). In this table, it is clearly observable that the mean scores for both groups

are close to each other which have meaning. The meaning for closeness in two groups mean scores indicates that both control and experimental group were at the same level of Listening Skills before administrating any treatment and providing them with any material.

Table 4.2. Mean, Variance and Standard Deviation of Posttests for Control and Experimental Groups					
	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Posttests	Control	30	11.0667	5.00299	25.030
	Experimental	30	16.5364	4.86885	23.706

Also, the descriptive analysis for the posttest scores of the control and the experimental group is shown in table (4.2). As is shown in this table, all the students in both control and experimental groups similar to table (4.1) are present. The mean for posttest scores of experimental groups is 16.53 as compared to the mean of posttest scores of the control which is 11.06. It is crystal clear that these two groups are different in overall mean; it implies that both groups of the study are at a different level of Listening Skills after the treatment process.

Table 4.3. Descriptive Analysis for the Pretest and the Posttest of Experimental Group of the Study					
Group	Tests	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Experimental	Pre	30	10.6667	5.28716	27.954
	Post	30	16.5364	4.86885	23.706

Table (4.3) shows the pretest mean for experimental group which is 10.66, as compared to the mean of same group posttest which is 16.53. As for the standard deviations obtained for the experimental group, there seems to be more variability among the pretest scores than the scores in the posttest.

Similarly, the descriptive analysis for the pretest and the posttest of control group of the study has been shown in table (4.4).

Table 4.4. Descriptive Analysis for the Pretest and the Posttest of Control Group of the Study					
Group	Test	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Control	Pre	0	10.5333	4.51613	20.395
	Post	0	11.0667	5.00299	25.030

According to this table, the mean for pretest of control group is 10.53 while the mean for its posttest score is 11.06.

4.3. Inferential Analysis of the Data

Inferential statistics are concerned with making predictions or inferences about a population from observations and analysis of a sample. That is, researchers can take the results of an analysis using a sample and generalize it to a larger population that the sample represents.

This section focused on inferential analysis of the obtained data of this study that was calculated

using SPSS, in which an Independent Sample T test was selected for calculating the t value and ANCOVA (general linear model/ Univariate) for calculating the covariance.

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	.040	.02	-2.720	58	.009	-3.46667	1.27457	-6.0179	-.91534
Equal variances not assumed			-2.720	57.957	.009	-3.46667	1.27457	-6.01803	-.91530

In order to show and understand whether the statistical difference occurred between two groups after treatment, there was a need to use an Independent Samples Test. The Independent Samples Test is a kind of parametric test which results in rejecting or supporting the hypothesis of the study. As it is shown in table (4.5) the t-value is calculated between the posttests of both control and experimental groups. The observed value shows to be -2.72 and the degree of freedom shows to be 57. Whether the level of significance equals to 0.02 the interpretation of data for rejecting or supporting the hypothesis of the study is possible.

The second type of inferential analysis of the data of the study is related to the degree of relationship between the pretest and posttest of Listening as a variable in both control and experimental groups. In the case of calculating and showing the progress of groups from pretests to posttests, two ANCOVAs were used.

Table 4.6. ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance) between Pretest and Posttest of Control Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5.506a	1	5.506	.214	.647
Intercept	660.864	1	660.864	25.687	.000
PreCo/PostCo	5.506	1	5.506	.214	.647
Error	720.361	28	25.727		
Total	4400.000	30			
Corrected Total	725.867	29			

a. R Squared = .008 (Adjusted R Squared = -.028)

Table 4.6 shows the covariates to be 0.214, which is the calculated value between the two sets of pretest and posttest scores in the control group using SPSS.

Table 4.7. ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance) between Pretest and Posttest of Experimental Group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	40.561 ^a	1	40.561	1.756	.196
Intercept	849.580	1	849.580	36.772	.000
PreEx/PostEx	40.561	1	40.561	1.756	.196
Error	646.905	28	23.104		
Total	7024.000	30			
Corrected Total	687.467	29			

a. R Squared = .059 (Adjusted R Squared = .025)

Also according to table (4.7) the obtained covariance value for experimental group is equal to 1.756. This table reveals that the progress in experimental group has occurred while table (4.6) indicated that the control group has not any progress. This means that the degree of statistical distance between the pretest and posttest scores in the experimental group is representative of the differences between the means in these two sets of scores.

Table 4.8. The Covariance for the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

	Between pre and posttests of the control group	Between pre and posttests of the experimental group
Covariance	.214	1.756

4.4. Results of Hypothesis Testing

In this section the result of hypothesis testing is presented and explained. Flashing back to the first chapter of the study, the question and the hypothesis of the study are remembered as below:

Q: Does digital proficiency affect Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills? H1: digital proficiency does not have any effect on Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills.

The hypothesis of the study which connoted the digital proficiency does not have any effect on Iranian Intermediate EFL learners' listening skills was rejected. Some evidence came to justify the reject of the hypothesis. First, the result of T-test as shown in table 4.5 implies that the observed t value is -2.720 in which the critical t value determined on the basis of considering the 2-tailed significance level of 0.05 is 2.000. Thus, the observed t was higher than the critical t and led to rejection of null hypothesis of the study. Also, according to the analysis of covariance illustrated in table (4.8) covariance value (1.756) is more than 1. Another evidence to justify the reject of the hypothesis was the value of level of significance calculated by SPSS that shows the value 0.843. Scientifically, the variability in the two sets of tests was significantly different.

4.5. Summary

This chapter embodied all data analysis gained from SPSS software which all shown in successive tables, and the statistical procedures and the related analysis of the findings were elaborated in detail. Based on the results of the study, the research question and hypothesis were discussed and in results and hypothesis testing section, the research hypothesis was rejected. The results proved that in experimental groups, there was a significant difference from pretest to posttest scores that led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result of this study suggests that using digital proficiency on the whole contributes to improving the students' language skills, in this case developing listening ability.

The results of this study reveal that using digital proficiency has a positive effect on the listening ability of the students.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Conclusion

5.1. Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to explore the Effectiveness of Digital Proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners' Listening Skills as well as their autonomy. Having employed SPSS, the researchers tested the research null-hypothesis formulated for the study. Results of t-test indicated positive effects of utilizing digital proficiency in EFL listening classrooms, apparently due to the experimental participants' increased engagement in class activities and tasks. Also, the students' enhancement may be as a result of an increased level of motivation to learn. The findings offer pedagogical implications for utilizing technological tools in EFL contexts which need to be motivating and enjoyable.

5.2. Pedagogical implications

Today's students are used to having technology at their fingertips. Audiobooks and digital texts can be accessed and read on a specialized e-book player, on the computer, over the Internet, via an iPod or over a cell phone. Schools should plan for multiple distribution channels so that students can easily access their digital texts anytime, anywhere, including outside of school. Not only will this support the struggling reader, but it will also help the busy student who will take advantage of reading books on his iPod while riding in the car to his soccer game.

Policymakers are already addressing the need for more digital text for students with print disabilities. In 2004, the Office of Special Education Programs, U.S. Department of Education, established two national centers at CAST to lead the development and support of the National Instructional Materials Accessibility Standard (NIMAS; U.S. Department of Education, 2006). NIMAS was also incorporated in the reauthorization of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act in 2004. While the legislation currently addresses the needs of individuals with print-related disabilities, publishers and software developers are already moving forward, thinking about the needs and preferences for students with and without disabilities. This will hopefully include discussions about the role of digital audio texts in learning as evidence

mounts regarding the powerful role listening can play in supporting other literacies such as reading.

5.3. Limitations

The limitations of the present study were as following: The present study explored the Effectiveness of Digital Proficiency on Iranian Intermediate EFL Learners' Listening Skills. This study was conducted at a language institute in Rasht. The subjects of the study were Intermediate learners learning English Other skills such as speaking, writing and reading were not taken into consideration. Only intermediate EFL students participated in this study and other EFL populations did not take part in the present study. Also, all of them were female

5.4. Suggestions for further research

Since it was clear from this study that Digital Proficiency is mainly a function of language proficiency, a future study could compare Digital Proficiency of both advanced and low proficient participants. Such study might yield more interesting results. A bigger size should be considered to obtain more significant results.

The subjects of this study were female. The similar study can be replicated with different sex and age distribution. The subjects of the study were intermediate learners. The similar study can be carried out regarding other levels of study such as pre-intermediate or advanced learners. The subjects of the study were English learners from language institute. Other studies can be replicated at the university levels with different major field of studies or those students majoring English.

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Appendix

Appendix A:

Oxford Placement Test

Oxford University Press and University of Cambridge Local Examination Syndicate

This test is divided into two parts:

Part One (Questions 1 – 40)

Part Two (Questions 41 – 60) – Time: 30 minutes

Part 1 Questions 1 – 5

• Where can you see these notices?

1. Please leave your room key at reception

A) in a shop

B) in a hotel

C) in a taxi

2. Foreign money changed here

A) in a library

B) in a bank

C) in a police station

3. AFTERNOON SHOW BEGINS AT 2 PM

- A) outside a theatre B) outside a supermarket C) outside a restaurant

4. CLOSED FOR HOLIDAY: Afternoon lessons start again on the 8th January

- A) at a travel agent's B) at a music school C) at a restaurant

5. Price per night: \$ 10 a tent; \$5 a person

- A) at a cinema B) in a hotel C) on a camp-site

Questions 6 – 10

- In this section you must choose the word which best fits each space in the text below.
- For questions **6** to **10**, mark **one** letter **A**, **B** or **C**

Scotland

Scotland is the north part of the island of Great Britain. The Atlantic Ocean is on the west and the North Sea on the east. Some people **(6)** _____ Scotland speak a different language called Gaelic. There are **(7)** _____ five million people in Scotland, and Edinburgh is **(8)** _____ most famous city. Scotland has many mountains; the highest one is called 'Ben

Nevis'. In the south of Scotland, there are a lot of sheep. A long time ago, there (9) _____ many forests, but now there are only a (10) _____. Scotland is only a small country, but it is quite beautiful.

6. A) on B) in C) at
7. A) about B) between C) among
8. A) his B) your C) its
9. A) is B) were C) was
10. A) few B) little C) lot

Questions 11 – 20

- In this section you must choose the word which best fits each space in the texts.
- For questions 11 to 20, mark **one** letter **A, B, C** or **D**

Alice Guy Blaché

Alice Guy Blaché was the first female film director. She first became involved in cinema whilst working for the Gaumont Film Company in the late 1890s. This was a period of great

change in the cinema and Alice was the first to use many new inventions, (11) _____ sound and color.

In 1907 Alice (12) _____ to New York where she started her own film company. She was (13) _____ successful, but when Hollywood became the center of the film world, the best days of the independent New York film companies were (14) _____. When Alice died in 1968, hardly anybody (15) _____ her name.

- | | | | | |
|-----|---------------|--------------|----------------|----------------|
| 11. | A) bringing | B) including | C) containing | D) supporting |
| 12. | A) moved | B) ran | C) entered | D) transported |
| 13. | A) next | B) once | C) immediately | D) recently |
| 14. | A) after | B) down | C) behind | D) over |
| 15. | A) remembered | B) realized | C) reminded | D) repeated |

UFOs: Do they exist?

UFO is short for 'unidentified flying object'. UFOs are popularly known as flying saucers, (16) _____ that is often the (17) _____ they are reported to be. The (18) _____ "flying saucers" were seen in 1947 by an American pilot, but experts who studied his claim decided it had been a trick of the light.

Even people experienced at watching the sky, (19) _____ as pilots, report seeing UFOs. In 1978 a pilot reported a collection of UFOs off the coast of New Zealand. A television

(20) _____ went up with the pilot and filmed the UFOs. Scientists studying this phenomenon later discovered that in this case they were simply lights on boats out fishing.

16. A) because B) therefore C) although D) so
17. A) look B) shape C) size D) type
18. A) last B) next C) first D) oldest
19. A) like B) that C) so D) such
20. A) camera man B) director C) actor D) announcer

Questions 21 – 40

- In this section you must choose the word or phrase which best completes each sentence.
- For questions 21 to 40, mark **one** letter A, B, C or D.

21. The teacher encouraged her students _____ to an English pen-friend.

- A) should write B) write C) wrote D) to write

22. They spent a lot of time _____ at the pictures in the museum.

- A) looking B) for looking C) to look D) to looking

23. Shirley enjoys science lessons, but all her experiments seem to _____ wrong.

- A) turn B) come C) end D) go

24. _____ from Michael, all the group arrived on time.

- A) Except B) Other C) Besides D) Apart

25. She _____ her neighbor's children for the broken window.

- A) accused B) complained C) blamed D) denied

26. As I had missed the history lesson, my friend went _____ the homework with me.

- A) by B) after C) over D) on

27. Whether she's a good actress or not is a _____ of opinion.

- A) matter B) subject C) point D) case

28. The decorated roof of the ancient palace was _____ up by four thin columns.

- A) built B) carried C) held D) supported

29. Would it _____ you if we came on Thursday?

- A) agree B) suit C) like D) fit

30. This form _____ be handed in until the end of the week.

- A) doesn't need B) doesn't have C) needn't D) hasn't got

31. If you make a mistake when you are writing, just _____ it out with your pen.

- A) cross B) clear C) do D) wipe

32. Although our opinions on many things _____, we're good friends.

- A) differ B) oppose C) disagree D) divide

33. This product must be eaten _____ two days of purchase.

- A) by B) before C) within D) under

34. The newspaper report contained _____ important information.

- A) many B) another C) an D) a lot of

35. Have you considered _____ to London?

- A) move B) to move C) to be moving D) moving

36. It can be a good idea for people who lead an active life to increase their _____ of vitamins.

- A) upturn B) input C) upkeep D) intake

37. I thought there was a _____ of jealousy in his reaction to my good fortune.

- A) piece B) part C) shadow D) touch

38. Why didn't you _____ that you were feeling ill?

- A) advise B) mention C) remark D) tell

39. James was not sure exactly where his best interests _____.

- A) stood B) rested C) lay D) centered

40. He's still getting _____ the shock of losing his job.

- A) across B) by C) over D) through

Part 2

Questions 41 – 50

• In this section you must choose the word or phrase which best fits each space in the texts.

• For questions 41 to 50, mark **one** letter **A, B, C** or **D**.

The tallest buildings - SKYSCRAPERS

Nowadays, skyscrapers can be found in most major cities of the world. A building which was many (41) _____ high was first called a skyscraper in the United States at the end of the 19th century, and New York has perhaps the (42) _____ skyscraper of them all, the Empire State Building. The (43) _____ beneath the streets of New York is rock, (44) _____ enough to take the heaviest load without sinking, and is therefore well-suited to bearing the (45) _____ of tall buildings.

41. A) stages B) steps C) storeys D) levels
42. A) first-rate B) top-class C) well-built D) best-known
43. A) dirt B) field C) ground D) soil
44. A) hard B) stiff C) forceful D) powerful
45. A) weight B) height C) size D) scale

SCRABBLE

Scrabble is the world's most popular word game. For its origins, we have to go back to the 1930s in the USA, when Alfred Butts, an architect, found himself out of **(46)** _____. He decided that there was a **(47)** _____ for a board game based on words and **(48)** _____ to design one. Eventually he made a **(49)** _____ from it, in spite of the fact that his original **(50)** _____ was only three cents a game.

46. A) earning B) work C) income D) job
47. A) market B) purchase C) commerce D) sale
48. A) took up B) set out C) made for D) got round
49. A) wealth B) fund C) cash D) fortune
50. A) receipt B) benefit C) profit D) allowance

Questions 51 – 60

- In this section you must choose the word or phrase which best completes each sentence.
- For questions **51** to **60**, mark **one** letter **A**, **B**, **C** or **D** on your Answer Sheet.

51. Roger's manager _____ to make him stay late if he hadn't finished the work.

- A) insisted B) warned C) threatened D) announced

52. By the time he has finished his week's work, John has hardly _____ energy left for the weekend.

- A) any B) much C) no D) same

53. As the game _____ to a close, disappointed spectators started to leave.

- A) led B) neared C) approached D) drew

54. I don't remember _____ the front door when I left home this morning.

- A) to lock B) locking C) locked D) to have locked

55. I _____ to other people borrowing my books: they always forget to return them.

- A) disagree B) avoid C) dislike D) object

56. Andrew's attempts to get into the swimming team have not _____ with much success.

- A) associated B) concluded C) joined D) met

57. Although Harry had obviously read the newspaper article carefully, he didn't seem to have _____ the main point.

- A) grasped B) clutched C) clasped D) gripped

58. A lot of the views put forward in the documentary were open to _____.

- A) enquiry B) query C) question D) wonder

59. The new college _____ for the needs of students with a variety of learning backgrounds.

A) deals B) supplies C) furnishes D) caters

60. I find the times of English meals very strange – I'm not used _____ dinner at 6pm.

A) to have B) to having C) having D) have

Appendix B: Pre-test of Listening

Total mark: / : Name

Class: Date:

Answer the following questions:

1- Part one

A) Look at the pictures and listen to what the people say. Number the pictures. (*Listen for specific information*)

c Mr Fahmy

f Mrs Zakariya

a Mr Abd El-Aziz

b Mrs Abd El-Salam

d Mrs El-Shazli

e Leila

B) Choose the right answer (*Listen for gist*)**What are these people talking about?**

- 1- Mr. Abdel-Aziz (T.V news- modern cars- the weather)
- 2- Mrs. Abdel-Salam (school classes- shopping-computers)
- 3-Mr. Fahmy (a new baby- school inspector-modern cars)
- 4-Mrs. El-Shazli (the weather-shopping-a new baby)
- 5- Mrs. Zakariya (friends-school classes- sky)
- 6- Mrs. Leila (a new baby- friends- the weather)

2- Part two

A. Azza is talking about her family photograph. Listen and write the phrases which tell you where the people are. (*Listen for making inference*)

1. Hatem isMona.
2. Selim is.....Karim.
3. Aza is.....
4. Nada is.....Mustafa.
5. Amr is.....

B. Now listen again and write the correct name under each member of the family.

(Listen for specific information)

Hatem –Karim- - Mustafa -Amr – Selim

3- Part three (Listen for detailed information)

A. Listen to four Londoners and their Egyptian friends talking about London. Tick (✓) for a favorable comment or cross (X) for unfavorable one on the topics each person mentions.

Archi tecture	Entert ainment	Cost of living	Saf ety	Public transport
Dan				
Jane				
Peter				
Rose				

Ali				
Azza				

B. Comprehension

Listen to the tape again and answer these questions.

- 1) Does Dan think that London is a more dangerous city than Johannesburg?
- 2) What does Jane complain about?
- 3) Which city is one of the most polluted in the world?
- 4) What do you think "the underground" is?
- 5) Does Azza like life in London?

c. Listen and complete (*Listen for making inference*)

- 1) Life in London isn't as.....as Johannesburg.
- 2) Prices in London are.....
- 3) The underground in London is.....
- 4) London is full ofplaces.
- 5) The entertainment in London is.....

4) *Part four (Listen for prediction)*

A) *Listen to a quizmaster asking questions about animals. Guess the names of the animals*

B) It is 5: 30 p.m. and these people are waiting for the bus. What are they going to do?

Listen and look at the pictures to make your guesses then complete the table.

1 It's five thirty in the evening and these people are waiting for the bus.
What do you think they are going to do tonight? Write one guess for each person.

<i>My guess</i>	<i>What they are going to do</i>

Listen and complete Name	What is he \ she going to do?
Michelle	
Kevin	
Robert	
Jane	

5- Part five (Listen for gist)

Listen to Ted, Wanda, Kim and Mike talking about their evening's activities.

Which subject does each person talk about?

Listen and match

- | | |
|----------|---------------------|
| 1- Ted | a) Playing football |
| 2- Wanda | b) Going jogging |
| 3- Kim | c) Going to the gym |
| 4- Mike | d) Playing tennis |

e) Playing the guitar

Scoring table:

part	quest ion	objectives	Total Score	S tudent score
Three	A	Measuring students' ability to: (1) listen for detailed information,	10	
B				
One	A	Measuring students' ability to: (1) Listen for specific information	10	

Two		B	
Two	A	Measuring students' ability to: (1) Listen for making inference, and	10
Three		C	
Four	A B	Measuring students' ability to: (1) Listen for prediction	10
One five	B	Measuring students' ability to: (1) listen for gist	10
Total			50

Appendix C: Post-test of Listening

Part A: Listen to the Audio and fill in the blanks

Randall: Hello. Today I'm interviewing Joshua on his (1) going to a Japanese school. Now Joshua, what time do you go to (2) ?

Joshua: Eight O'clock.

Randall: Eight O'clock. And do you (3) by yourself, or on a school bus?

Joshua: No, I have a group that goes with me.

Randall: So you go with a group?

Joshua: (4) .

Randall: Now what (5) of things do you take to school?

Joshua: I take my taiso fuku, that is gym clothes, and I take my backpack and my books [Oh, okay] and (6) like that

Part B: Listen again and choose the best answer

1. How does Joshua go to school in Japan?

- A. He takes a school bus every morning
- B. He rides the subway at 8:00 AM.

- C. He walks with a group of students.

2. Which item did Joshua NOT mention when talking about the things he takes to school?

- A. backpack
- B. gym clothes
- C. school hat

3. What is one of the first things Joshua does when he arrives at school?

- A. He practices his reading and writing.
- B. He stands and bows to the teacher.
- C. He puts on his gym clothes for class.

4. Where does Joshua eat lunch at school?

- A. in his classroom
- B. in the lunchroom
- C. in the gymnasium

5. What time does Joshua probably get home from school most days?

- A. between 1:00 PM and 2:00 PM
- B. between 2:00 PM and 3:00 PM
- C. between 3:00 PM and 4:00 PM